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Value Co-creation in Digital Design through Visual Exploratory Assessment

POSTDOCTORAL FINAL REPORT

PROJECT SUPERVISION

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GLOSSARY

LSP – Lego Serious Play

LMD – Learning Module Design

Co-creation – Development supported by peer interaction

VNA – Visual Narrative Art

Visual Curation – Search and organization of visual elements to form a statement

Trans codification – Translating external information into a familiar code

1 STUDY JUSTIFICATION

The present post-doctoral study focused on the foundation of Digital Design project ideation supported by exploratory studies.

The research project aims to focus on the orientation problems detected at the start of a design project. The orientation problems may result from the absence of diagnostic or exploratory studies. These studies could enhance systematization, visual literacy, and argumentation skills.

In the context of teaching-learning in Digital Design, there is a difficulty on the part of students in systematizing thinking. When presenting a project, the sudden and accelerated development of solutions results in unfocused projections sowing frustration in its authors.

This situation relates to the ability of students to argue in the conduct of the project. A visual literacy of culturally contextualized elements benefits the argument of a project.

The argumentation of conducting a project which does not contain a phase of diagnosis reflected presents weaknesses that compromise its execution and defense - discussion.

The Digital Design project is perennial the development of critical assertions instead of solutions obtained by artificial intelligence. In contemporary society, we live under the influence of Big Data that aims to build solutions at the level of artificial intelligence. Companies like Adobe Systems have collected user data from their software solutions since 1999. This company uses this data to develop solutions that shortly, illusorily, will give the idea of the autonomy of various digital systems of graphic composition. Naively many organizations will be seduced by these volatile solutions, causing drastic changes in employability factors and the skills required of designers. If, on the one hand, artificial intelligence "seems" to accelerate the processes of developing technical solutions (and often arising from trend engines also aesthetic solutions), the critical analysis derived from emotional literacy on cultural variants remains a human domain. It is, therefore, necessary to reinforce this aspect with a "look around" before we put ourselves behind the digital window, in a 360° perspective, so often used superficially by the advertising industry is increasingly pressing for our future. The gaze refers not only to the problem's visuality but also to its tactile and human qualities. In the action of "looking around," the reasons, the framework, and the duration of an event can be collected. These elements can provide information because the digital display is a window, not a mere technological extension.

In the teaching of Digital Design, the form and function relationship and the distinction between Art and Design are present.

Their characteristics of coding and temporality distinguish both. However, if, on the one hand, Art, in its communication, uses codes derived from the language of the author and is sought an effect of crystallization, Design uses its communication codes appropriate to the interpretation of a consumer audience with specific characteristics (temporal, social and cultural). Because it is associated with a productive aspect, Design must relate to a functional character in project development, specifically in teaching-learning, distancing itself from the cryptic concept of the word "talent," a word that remains a contradictory concept of Art in the teaching of Design.

Orientation and training should be inclusive and accessible and there should be a set of practices consistent with the goals of the profession. If we develop a briefing based on a planned product model, we have to explain the cultural constraints. How is it possible to assess quality when there are no literacy bases in students? How to measure the success of the conduction of a project when the cultural distinctions of the possible audiences are not made visible? How can a student working group communicate if they have not dealt with a product's narrative extensions?

The article "Image and Brand Diagnostic Applied to Ux Design" (Jose Silva, 2014a) provided the interest to develop the presented research. The article focused on the use of an imaging diagnostic methodology through the interpretation of the author José Martins on the archetypes of Carl Jung. José Martins developed a structure of archetypes that in this article was applied in the characterization of a brand.

Hypothesis

In this research is presented as a hypothesis, the potential of **Vna's** as a support in the development of graphics solutions and a support leverage in the argumentation and conduction of the project.

2 OBJECTIVES

The following objectives frame the research on the study of exploratory strategies as project foundation.

General Objectives

This research project aims to explore the use of exploratory visual assessments as an element of exploration of a Digital Design project;

- Create a contribution to the teaching of design on the issue of visual literacy based on cultural references and to;
- Foster interest in the construction of project value by promoting visual literacy elements and creating visual narratives.

Specific Objectives

Regarding the specific objectives, this study aims to;

- Explore the possibilities of co-creation arising from a visual exploratory phase.
- Contribute to an interventionist research methodology to build, with the use of Vna's (Visual Narrative Art Boards), an initial element of project development;
- Value integrative creative methodologies that converge in a learning group;
- Contribute to a basis for critical reflection prior to digital interaction and manipulation.

3 METHODOLOGY

This research lies within the framework of a qualitative research. The qualitative research produces holistic readings of rich, contextual and generally unstructured and non-numerical information (Mason, 2002). The defining characteristic of case study research is its focus on the questions of "how" and "why" (Myers, 2009) and for this reason it is appropriate for descriptive and exploratory studies (Mouton, 2001).

Within the qualitative research, the research focused a concatenated exploration. The expression concatenated exploration refers at once to a research process and the resulting set of field studies that are linked together (Stebbins, 2001). According with the same author the essence of this facet of exploration lies in its continuous interstudy comparisons of groups, activities, or processes. In principle, these studies could be carried out simultaneously, were it not for two procedural matters.

The research portrayed in this article follows a methodology Quasi experimental, focused on those situations in which the experimenter cannot manipulate behavior but in which the logic of experimental design still may be applied. These situations have been commonly regarded as "quasi-experimental" situations. Developed in the scope of an exploratory, an exploratory study answers 'what', 'who', 'where' questions, and is intended "to develop pertinent hypotheses and propositions for further inquiry", that is, to help find a research focus when the understanding is still insufficient or lacking (Yin & SAGE., 2003).

The Learning experiences portrayed in the exploratory assessment, involved sessions structured sequentially. The learning experience followed the strategy of constructionism according to the idea of learning-by-making of Papert (1991) moreover, applied principles related to implicit learning, implicit learning heavily relates to Teacher beliefs, those in turn influenced by both personal and professional experience. These beliefs, once generated, create base structures for the construction of experiences. Mary Kennedy (1997) suggests that new ideas that are compatible with an existing framework will be easily assimilated, whereas ideas that appear challenging to, or incompatible with the framework will be dismissed.

The next chapter presents the theoretical framework, that explores the concept of of Visual Diagnostic Exploratory Study, as other structural concepts the provides supports to the subsequent exploratory assessment's resultant from the research dissemination.

4 THEORETHICAL FRAMEWORK

The co-creation value is part of the creation of rich interactions at the level of project problematization, facilitated by visual exploration.

In the context of visual exploratory evaluation, we can refer to visual narrative art (Megehee & Spake, 2012) when mapping of narratives through the arrangement of visual elements (photographs, drawings or symbols). Through this assembly it is possible to extract implicit meanings. Nonverbal VNAs are one of the oldest ways to narrate stories and create meaning and remain a form of communication of the 21st century. The development of VNAs also allows to inform and describe archetypal transformations of products and services

In this research we propose to empirically examine the proposition that by creating and interpreting VNAs, in the context of a diagnostic practice in Digital Design projects, in the context of teaching - learning, is a valuable contribution to make aware and visible the implicit meanings contained in stories, which would otherwise remain obscure in the foundation of the project. This visibility will co-create value to the project by "bringing implicit narrative elements" to the surface. This study will explain the process of creating VNAs, include examples of process results with interpretations, and provide a contribution to the level of teaching practices in Design.

The creation and interpretation of VNAs arises in the context of diagnostic practices that occur at the beginning of a Digital Design project. We differentiate in this study, "diagnosis" of "exploratory studies". Diagnosing refers to determining and knowing a problem by studying its symptoms and analyzing the various investigations conducted, while exploratory studies refer to an operation or procedure whose purpose is to allow knowledge of the state of a non-visible element. Diagnosis refers to the testing process of how a result is obtained (Zwaga et al., 1998). This method is used in several areas to descriptively identify a problem (Sullivan, 2009). In the context of this investigation the term "diagnosis" has a double meaning, we can observe it as informative or symbolic. Its Informative nature refers to a set of processes conducted for a particular purpose; the symbolic character because they contain a metaphor communicated to the students. According to Geary (2011) a metaphor by juxtaposing two different things distorts our point of view, so that unexpected similarities emerge.

Design thinking helps to curate and to “drill down” to the essence of an issue and see what matters. (Jeanne et al., 2013). “Curation is where acts of selecting and arranging add value.” “Put together, such acts are an extraordinary store of value for an overloaded world.” (Eliot, 2010) When designing “information maps”, the design team can focus on what is essential for a certain segment of users. This “curation” aspect is key to both design thinking and Agile-styled methodologies. In design thinking, curation happens with the identification of key insights and the creation of design criteria. These critical activities allow us to take all of the *What is* research and translate it into a simple set of criteria to drive idea generation in the *What if* phase (Jeanne et al., 2017).

The curation necessity is also observed in technology, specifically in Curated computing, that presents era of personal computing where choice are constrained but the experience is more relevant and it's necessary because the portable devices, where the experiences that governed laptops and desktops in the past just aren't appropriate for the form factor you need a simpler experience and so you can think of this as a trip to the museum where a curator of that museum has very intentionally chosen just a few objects to put into a gallery she's interpreted them she's decided what path you're going to take through the gallery so that it's a meaningful experience, what it's basically saying is that less is more, we're an era where consumers actually have less choice for their experience to be more relevant (Sarah, 2010)

Related with the problem of curating source of information Designers' use of both physical and digital sources of inspiration during the conceptualizing phase of design projects is well established, especially when collaborating with others, The materials designers collect can result in the construction of mood boards used to help support idea development and analysis as well as helping the designer express perceptions about a design brief (Porcheron et al., 2016)

In Mosaic configurations, we saw evidence that the design of a creative community can affect users' views on what type of content is valuable and useful for the rest of the community. Many existing creative communities are *creator-centric*, meaning that they focus primarily on allowing creators to share their own content in publicly viewable portfolios. However, communities can also be *curator-centric*, and focus more on allowing creators (or fans) to showcase or curate the work of others; the platform Pinterest, where users can gather content in themed “boards,” is one example of a community designed around social content curation. These design attitudes are not mutually exclusive, as many communities (including DeviantArt) also support curation by allowing users to favorite work by others and organize and share these favorites (Kim et al., 2017).

The need for curation is currently recurrent, in the context of learning, in visual literacy exercises, in the need for control over images not generated for the purpose of a certain research (Leon, 2015).

Curation makes information mining much more efficient. Content curation is not about collecting links or being an information pack rat, it is more about putting them into a context with organization, annotation, and presentation. Content curators provide a customized, vetted selection of the best and most relevant resources on a very specific topic or theme (P & Thilagavathy, 2016).

Recent research on social media shows the importance of curation on deletion of social media highlights users' on-going curation work, work that is triggered especially due to life changing circumstances. The conceptualization of social media as enduring exhibition highlights a form of curation work. The enduring 'exhibition' of personal data, and recent work around deletion highlights the problem of keeping social media on display. Content that does not fit the way one wishes to present oneself must be removed. This concern with audience and self-presentation contrasts with the curation work that underpins more personal archives from users (Zhao & Lindley, 2014).

Images provide a useful starting place for understanding visual consumption. Specifically, they allow:

- **sensory anchoring:** interpretation is anchored in the image; • instant access – references to images can be made and checked in an iterative process;
- **personal engagement:** images hold and draws our attention. Much interpretation is a blend of passionate encounter and critical concern.
- **wide-spectrum cognition:** images engage a variety of cognitive processes;
- **multi connectedness:** images are rooted in culture.

Moreover, working with visual communication is an effective means to introduce and develop critical thinking – higher-order cognition that is essential for intellectual work. Management (Perkins, 1994)

There is a shift in understanding from a person (a curator) to an enterprise (curating) which is now understood as an activity unto itself. There is, currently, a certain resonance between the idea of curating and the contemporary idea of the creative self, making aesthetic choices of where to go and what to eat, wear and do.

The current vogue for the idea of curating stems from a feature of modern life: the proliferation and reproduction of ideas, raw data, processed information, images, disciplinary knowledge and material products that we are witnessing today. This is hard to overstate. But though the explosive effects of the Internet. The exponential increase in the amount of data created by human societies is a basic fact of our time. The result, arguably, has been a shift in the ratio of importance between making new objects and choosing from what is already there. (Hans, 2014) The *act* of making the obscure more visible can be a valuable contribution (Colin, 2014).

In the subject of image curation specifically in the art world, there is also an authoring process, as the process of choosing and displaying images, defines and creates an itinerary. According to Rugg and Sedgwick (Rugg & Sedgwick, 2007) in 1972, the artist Daniel Buren wrote 'Exhibition of an Exhibition', where he claimed that: 'More and more, the subject of an exhibition tends not to be the display of artworks, but the exhibition of the exhibition as a work of art.' (See Buren 2004: 26.) At the time, Buren was referring both specifically to the work of curator Harald Szeemann and his curation of *Documenta 5*, and to the emergence of the idea of exhibition organizer as author. The 'fragments' and other 'details' exhibited, in most cases are entirely foreign the authorial exhibition.

The logic of the ecosystem is built for the purpose of curation (selecting and organizing) by the author of the exhibition

According with Arnoldus (2010) Digital culture opens up new challenges for curation. The general public run the risk of being swamped by the information that is out there in the digital domain. It would be good to note the spectrum (new) methods and channels used to collect and select information and sources, under the new paradigm everyone more or less become a curator, the general public show an interest in taking part in the act of curation.

Accordingly with (2017) Designers can use maps to curate and synthesize their observations, mapmaking include three basic activities: capture, curation, and analysis. When documenting a physical condition using a basic tool like the camera. The camera takes, processes, manipulates and shares images in a matter of minutes. Although the time to get data is shorter, the complexity and amount of data makes curation more difficult. In design fields this means translating sense data, visual observation, data collected through different means into legible output impacting the design process. Maps and mapping can be a mean to curate information.

There is a growing use of the word "curated" to describe what the authors of blogs and other online spaces actually do. Whereas in earlier times, the opposite verbs used to credit an author would have been simply "written," "edited," or even "created," it is quite clear that they don't capture all the self-representational activities or *practices* in digital culture that the verb "curated" does. This is because *curating* a space is not only about writing or creating within it but also collecting, distributing, assembling, disassembling, and moving it across different stages. In other words, it is an active practice that is larger in its reach, scope, and nature than the others but which contains and subsumes them (Potter, 2012). According to the same author Curatorship is a form of meta authorship, understanding the relationships between texts of all kinds: moving image, still image, print, and more.

Accordingly with Williams (2009), Individuals are capturing and storing an ever-increasing amount of digital information about or for themselves, including documents, articles, portfolios of work, digital images, and audio and video recordings. Computer processing, storage, and software tools are increasing in power year on year. Many issues arise from this increasingly empowered landscape of personal collection, dissemination, and digital memory. Personal information collections and management have been the focus of attention of researchers for many years, particularly in the field of Human-Computer Interaction (e.g. Malone, 1983). However, the rapid rise in digital applications and storage capacity has both stimulated interest in this field and also opened up a new research area within it highlighted by Beagrie (2005). In particular, the way individuals use their personal computers. The authors adopt the term “personal digital archives” to refer to these informal, diverse, and expanding memory collections created or acquired and accumulated and maintained by individuals in the course of their personal lives, and belonging to them, rather than to their institutions or other places of work. The personal archive of a living person is a dynamic entity. New objects are created; others are amended; some are discarded. Yet the parallel is in fact an apt one as well as a useful one: for increasingly, professional curators of contemporary personal archives are engaged in creative activities that supplement the original contents of an archive.

In a classroom environment, exploratory studies alongside diagnostic, allow students to filter elements to ascertain the project scope. Creative approaches toward problem-solving in digital design projects play an increasingly significant role since they enable an immersion on a hypothetical scenario of consumption. The diagnosis involves the survey of a significant array of visual data and trends. After data collection regarding the consumer of a specific product, students will proceed with the analysis of the selected visual samples. The arrangement of those samples will be determined by them in order to provide visual clues.

Regarding this approach, the authors Wong et al. (2013) developed FaceGrid, an interactive multimedia art project. Inspired by photography and cinematographic montage concept, FaceGrid used multiple small image tiles woven and stitched together to form the pixel art design pattern. This project documents ways of living and habits of ordinary individuals in a multi-cultural and diverse ethnic society in Malaysia. Through several slices of audio-visual documentation, the authors captured and archive the different facets of people lives and stories. The project was described as a continuous exercise to accumulate a group of experiences, stories artifacts in a unified platform. When the authors implemented FaceGrid, they didn't have time to discuss the feasibility of their research method in the context of interaction design and visual methodology. However, the photo-documentation method turned out to be as a rigorous visual method in the design process. The same method allowed a detailed and thorough approach regarding visual documenting related to the social practices of the individuals observed. It also provided an external view of the process to the future development of the project.

Though considering the contemporary technological acceleration and dispersion, the employment of this method in a classroom requires an adjustment and an itinerary designed in several stages. According to Clarke (2017), the new age of media, that accelerated and facilitated access to information changed the perspective on traditional educational subjects, teachers are now encouraged to introduce technology into their pedagogy. The author also offers a particular view, in which teachers can creatively introduce a new and useful strategy known as Instructional Digital Storytelling (IDS), guided by a Technological, Pedagogical and Content (TPACK) structure. Clarke (2017) illustrates how through narrative inquiry, the creation and the use of Digital Storytelling, for instructional purposes in classroom settings, highlighted challenges, rewards, accelerated learning and developed a community of practice across disciplines. The author's main idea is the experience of creating a Digital Storytelling in four levels:

- a) Internal structures of blending voice-over, imagery, and sound to create a successful IDS;
- b) Experience of challenges and negotiations in crafting stories;
- c) Experience of sharing with students;
- d) Recognition of themes and patterns, which may have emerged among the participants.

For Clarke, the IDS refer to an effort toward Visual Storytelling structuring, in order to achieve a guided creative itinerary. However, having a guiding strategy does not guarantee the richness of creative possibilities.

To find new creative possibilities requires a change of perspective. The History of Art provides an interesting example in Romanticism. The Romantic artistic and intellectual movement that originated in Europe in the late eighteenth century, with its peak in the approximate period from 1800 to 1850, attached great importance to changing creative perspectives. Charles Rosen (1998) quoted the German poet Novalis also known as Friedrich von Hardenberg: - "making the familiar strange, and the strange familiar". This statement defined the romantic art. The Novalis' concept was closely related with surrealism and defended among other romantic theorists like Wordsworth and Coleridge. According to Shklovsky, Novalis considered as creative strategies the production of short stories fragmented and without appearing logic but linked with meaningful associations, like dreams. Novalis also referred the feeling that poets, painters, and musicians had about the freedom of their work, the endowment to manipulate forms, symbols, and notes seemingly without a suggestion to reality outside itself. The creative technique of fragmentation, however, requires a framework, in the attempt to project different cohesive solutions.

Throughout history, artists and designers always pursued the freedom of creativity. Artists were owners of their codes, designers' developers of solutions according to the social and cultural codes of an audience. In the 1950s, George M. Prince and William J. J. Gordon, while working at the Invention Design Group, (based at the Arthur D. Little Consulting Company), developed a creative method called Synectics. According to Wake (2000), the term Synectics comes from the Greek *synektikos*, which means the joining of different and not evident or irrelevant elements into a unified "whole". Synectics is an approach to promoting creativity that is compatible with design paradigms. Synectics was introduced to the public in the 1960s with the publication of William Gordon's book: Synectics. In the book, the author presented a method that combined interaction practices with a creative process centered on the use of metaphor and the incorporation of analogies from several disciplines, **Table 1**.

Add	Transfer	Change Scale	Distort	Prevaricate
Subtract	Empathize	Substitute	Disguise	Analogize
Repeat	Animate	Fragment	Contradict	Hybridize
Combine	Superimpose	Isolate	Parody	Metamorphose
Symbolize	Mythologize	Fantasize		

Table 1 - Gordon's Synectic Trigger Mechanisms

The application of Synectic trigger mechanisms can generate new thoughts, designs and inventions. The "add" operator may imply extending, expanding, developing, supplementing, or broadening our reference subject (ex. consumer goods). We can evidence the subject significance or find ways to make *it denote*. The "combine" operator implies *gathering things together*. We can connect, attach, unify, mix, merge or gather. The merge and join paradigms provide a menu of useful operators for combining elements. The "Synectic Think Cycle" involves three interrelated modes of thinking that can be applied to structure these processes. Roukes (1988) describes these as the Synectic "three Rs, consisting of:

Referring: Defines the general subject and specific problem. Referring also involves the gathering of background information on the problem.

Reflecting: Involves the creative manipulation of the problem, exploring the various alternatives, possible solutions, and translations of various types.

Reconstruction: Is the process of reinventing or transforming. It involves the Synectic trigger mechanisms and the possibility of applying it as paradigm superimpositions. Reconstruction can imply deferring apart the problem or its existing solution assembling it in a different way. This process is cyclic: after the reconstruction phase, students can repeatedly return to the referring stage as they explore variations.

The application of these methods uses the mnemonic capacity as a "mirror of creativity" where the stimulus triggers creativity. Buzan (2006) mentioning memory, argues that creative thinking works with imagination and association. By linking item A to item B, it is produced a new innovative idea, *far from the norm*, which we call "creative." The processes of mnemonic and creative thought are therefore identical in structure - the only difference is in the intention. A "mnemonic device" associates two items to help the brain to remember (re-create) a third image in the future. A creative operation also combines two elements to design a third party in the future, but the original goal is to change or affect the future in some way, while the mnemonic goal is merely *to remember*. Thus, by creating mnemonic diagrams with visually presented information, students are simultaneously training their faculties of creative thinking. As Novalis remarked: - "making the familiar strange and the strange familiar," the mind can reproduce changes in perspective, separate an idea from conventional boundaries, and thus provide a volumetric perception of what sometimes appears to be a "surface" of an idea.

As referred by Boden (2004), only the mind changes the impossible to the possible, transforming computational 'cannot' into computational 'can'. The provided structure must allow *playing around the problem*. As the same author (2004, p. 58) refers: nothing is more natural than 'playing around' to stimulate the potential – and the limits – of a given way of thinking.

Drawing an analogy between different structures, for instance, helps us to see what kind of results the creative reasoning can and cannot produce. Often the "results" materialize in analogies', but this is only possible for someone with the relevant literacy about the subject in question, someone able to recognize analogies. An analogy is crucial to creative thinking, in science and the arts, and essential to the *hunch of discovery*, based on some expertise. This type of reasoning can produce topological changes, since topology is concerned with a neighbor-relations. Ball (2009) refers that the analogical reasoning involves accessing and transferring previous knowledge of objects, attributes and relations to support current problem-solving and decision-making activities. The *hunch moment of a solution* may have a relation to the level of immersion in a specific problem. Thus, storytelling has the potential to increase the level of immersion in problem-solving.

This proposed strategy works as a diagnostic in a Digital Design project focused on the development of a product. The visual clues extracted from that exercise would result in two organized mosaics. According to William and Lidwell (2003) the Persona refers to a method that uses fictional users or consumers to guide decision-making concerning characteristics, interactions, and aesthetics. The information gathered related to a hypothetical consumer of the product or service will constitute one of the mosaics mentioned. The same authors point that this method uses fictional users or consumers to highlight characteristics and personal preferences of the possible ones. A Persona is normally constituted by a photo-representation, name, short description and details about specific interests and daily routine. The Personas' conception requires dramatization guided by cultural and social institutions. In accordance with the flow of this strategy, it is essential to build and maintain the pace of the Persona's assemblage so that students can find and act on the information that comes out of their gathering (Adlin & Pruitt, 2010).

The concept of transdisciplinary adopted follows the perspective of Findeli (2008) The transdisciplinary step is different. The situation that requires it is not that of a project of knowledge (observation, description, interpretation, understanding, etc.) of the world, but that of its transformation. The perspective is projective/creative and requires knowledge to be engaged in the project.

The concept of co-creation very present in the construction of consumer environments, Creating an experience environment in which consumers can have active dialogue and co-construct personalized experiences is a valuable contribution to project systematization (Pralhalad & Ramaswamy, 2004).

The perspective of consumption links to the context of Consumer of Visual texts, in that frame, consumer engage in a dialogue of co-creation. The co-creation approach to process design involves several different stakeholders, exploring their experiences, organizing participatory workshops for improving interactions and building platforms for new interactions and continuous dialogue. (Ramaswamy & Gouillart, 2010), co-creation is widely understood as practices where a design practice and one or more communities of practice participate in creating new desired futures. The co-creation is widely understood as practices where a design practice and one or more communities of practice participate in creating new desired future (Holmlid et al., 2015).

This research follows a combination of a viewpoint that aims to develop a nature of Learning that draws on research describing both cognitive social and cultural perspectives. Cognitive in the perspective of attention, selection, retrieval, mental models, schema, and cognitive overload. Social in the perspective of *situativity* theory, discourse analysis, critical realism. Cultural in the perspective of Anthropological approaches to *situativity* and community formation, structural and post-structural analysis.

In this sense, the focus lies on the designer's ability to develop diagnostics competences within the scope of a project. The following example regarding the development of a visual diagnostic exploratory study illustrates how the learning perspective is applied. The model developed focuses on a visual diagnostic exploratory study, joins cognitive, social, and cultural perspectives to support the argumentation and project conduction in the following phases of prototype development and project argumentation.

Given the wide variety of visual information available in different media and contexts, it becomes difficult for Design students to start a Design project without developing support that delimits the development of future graphics solutions framed culturally. There is some controversy with the designation "diagnosis," this term is chosen because it has a double meaning. According to the Oxford dictionary, "diagnosis" means "the act of discovering or identifying the exact cause of an illness or a problem."

The communication of the concept of Visual Diagnostic Exploratory Study involves the use of metaphors applied to facilitate students' access to the use of the Visual diagnostic exploratory study as a strategy for collecting and analyzing information, **Figure 01**.

visual diagnostic exploration study

Images of
cultural
stereotypes

A metaphor that
communicates
the need for a
previous study
before the project
intervention

Without constrains

Analysis and
identification
of codes

Figure 01

The meaning of the Visual diagnostic exploratory study as a strategy to collect information.

The word "diagnosis" serves as a metaphor for the exploratory study of visual diagnosis, as a part of a problem-solving logic. This metaphor also aims to motivate students in collecting information that delimits the issues associated with the development of the project.

The visual diagnostic exploratory study combines several aspects of image contextualization according to emotional archetypes, an interpretive code of product through the discovery of keywords, and the construction of a narrative according to a principle of the consumer journey. This diagnostic aims to introduce the development of visual design solutions, creating a basis for image reasoning.

Certain theoretical concepts can be used as information filters and are quite useful in exploratory studies to determine cultural contexts (Jose Silva et al., 2016). The experience of image diagnostic through exploratory studies allows students to "feel" the rationale of their argument and to structure what are archetypal influences according to contemporary tendencies and ways of making explicit familiar knowledge to those who construct the diagnostic study, (Jose Silva, 2012, 2014b; José Silva et al., 2017).

Building a Design Project Leveraged by a Diagnostic Phase highlights the use of image mosaics, a concept that can be related to the concept of bricolage. According to the perspective of anthropologist Claude Levi-Strauss, bricolage is the skill of using whatever is at hand and recombining them to create something new. For Levi-Strauss, the bricoleur, who is the savage mind, works with his hands in devious ways, puts pre-existing things together in new ways, and makes whatever with the hand (Mambrol, 2016).

The diagnostic strategy brings together three tools for collecting information; the gathering of information from emotional archetypes according to an interpretive model of Martins (2007), the definition of cultural code according to Rapaille (2008) and customer journey by Følstad (2018). The students applied this macro strategy in the development of exploratory studies related to their final degree project; a project course taught in the second semester of the study cycle. The diagnostic strategy has the potential to increase the acuity of the qualitative information to signal not only the communication of the product but also its perspective of use.

From a scientific point of view, the theoretical component aims to allow a repetition of the experience, thus contributing to questions regarding the clarity of the method used. A Design Theory can be integrated into the context of Design Science Research to make the connection between the design and the knowledge base more transparent (Pirainen & Briggs, 2011).

"To expand our ability to see to understand a visual message and, even more crucial, to make a visual message." (Dondis, 1973). We live in an era where there is a large amount of visual information, mixed in a fog of noise that makes it difficult to focus on the image's communication qualities. Accordingly, with Watzman (1999) the problem is that no one has given us a more exceptional ability to use and understand all this new information. In our rush to use enticing new tools, we have forgotten our goal: that this is all about quality communication. We need to step back and evaluate this visual chaos; learn to see, not just look; learn and understand what the basic principles are to create quality communication as well as the implications of our choices. Our education has made us verbally literate; we must now become visually literate.

Visual rhetoric is a type of non-discursive rhetoric that focuses on the ability of a visual image to communicate a compelling message. A visual image that communicates a message is a document that results from a Design process. A document is rhetorical, according to Sharf (1979), Bridgeford (2018) defines designers to label anyone who is making an attempt to use a structure and adapt it to serve a purpose.

Hart (2005) defines rhetoric as the art of using language to help people narrow their choices among specifiable, if not specified, policy options. The rhetoric image can also relate to an interpretive theory that frames a message as an interested party's attempt to influence and audience, according to Scott (1994). Moreover, Foss (2017) calls it the action humans perform when they use symbols to communicate with one another. Artistic considerations, as well as logical ones, support effective rhetoric. As Hart (2005) refers to both the artist and the persuader use their imaginations to engage their audiences' imaginations. For Campbell (2008), Rhetoric is the study of what is persuasive. It examines social truths, addressed to others, justified by reasons that reflect cultural values. In all types of rhetoric, some senders select formal elements (arguments) and arrange them in terms of their expectations about how their listeners or viewers will perceive and interpret these elements (Burke, 1969). This perspective links to rhetorical criticism, a process of systematically investigating and explaining symbolic acts and artifacts to understand rhetorical processes, (Foss, 2017). The purpose of this article is a contribution to how to improve the effectiveness of a design exploratory study. Investigate how to develop guided interpretations of visual design messages according to information filters that tailor the visual message to a specific audience.

5 EXPLORATORY ASSESSMENTS

5.1 Introduction to Chapter

Although they represent various research applications, the following studies, developed throughout research and dissemination, aimed to meet the general and specific objectives presented at the beginning of this report.

This section comprises the following exploratory assessments:

- NEOD Model
- Product and brand, design insights from myth dissemination - Learning module design
- Visual Cartography Project
- Learning Creative Strategy - An Itinerary Through a Mosaic of Visual Clues
- Visual Diagnostic Exploratory Study
- Exploring climate change through LSP – A Learning Experience
- Visual Storytelling – Creative Strategy of Visual Clues
- Innovation in Traditional Productive Sectors - Visual Curation in Design

5.2 NEOD Model

New challenges arise when encouraging design students to focus the subject of image diagnostics. The present development in product communication and consumer behaviors requires new specialties, skills and competences from design students.

The described experimental module of learning designed for the course of Research Design, degree of Visual Communication and Audiovisual Production, Applied Arts Superior School Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Portugal was implemented in the second semester on the academic year of 2016/17. The module had the duration of fifteen sessions. The learning design experiment focused a product communication project.

The experimental module aimed on delivering a sequence of activities that would result in a better outcome in the information analysis and image output. This project allowed students to work with product communication, helping them reasoning how message and context infer into a product image and values. The module focused on a learning experiment on student's better argumentation and justification on different contexts of qualitative analysis.

The Learning module comprises eight weeks of activity distributed in introductory - argumentation, development, test and exposition activities. In the introduction, students implement problem diagnostic and image diagnostic. The problem diagnostic focuses on finding unsolved situations where a visual concept could be a real communication contribution to a persona group, also focuses in the communication limits and context of use. The Learning module also centers on finding the business model related to the structural concept in the proposed communication, when testing the scenario, students discuss the cultural | political and social implications of a proposed model of communication. The image diagnostic works parameters related to the cultural image framework, archetypes and the cultural code related with the project.

For the learning module distribution of learning materials and discussion the classroom will work with the digital platform Trello. This platform allows a horizontal distribution of materials and allows simple actions related with tasks and project management, furthermore it provides an inter face with a very short learning curve.

The proposed learning module, in the diagnostic phase, presents to students the chance to work on a specific briefing and processing the information through different filters. In the project sequence, the image diagnostic research, can retrieve useful data, for future overall aesthetic quality. In the project design scope, the image diagnostic, works the image boundaries and limits, in a more efficient and sequential fashion. The proposed aesthetic solutions must be coherent with the communication strategy underway.

The NEOD (Narrative experience-oriented diagnostic) process comes as contribute for a better reasoning on the diagnostic project grounds. Allows a better arrangement in the project tools, allowing a sequence of information filters, empowering in students a structured view avoiding hasty feedbacks in project conduction.

The project must balance two "strings" in the accessibility settings, the external perspective (visual) and the internal (the structure). The low context is present in the image surface effectiveness in communicating the message, but well adapted to a high context where visual reasoning is key in designing visual communication and where the expressiveness (aesthetic feedback) from the visual concept is crucial.

The two elements must be tuned with perception, the process by which individuals select, organize, and evaluate stimuli from the environment to provide meaningful experiences for themselves (Adler & Gundersen, 2007, p. 71).

In the first level of experience students prepare a sequence of questions related with the product experience. Although they can use on a specific focus group, closed or open questions about the product focused on the project, those have only a purpose of assuring the interviewed panel about the focus group contribution in defining the possible qualities or defects present in the product. The real "questions" came afterwards in their experience description, made anonymous. After analyzed it will give information about the most important aspects related with the product.

The second phase of diagnostic addressed the persona evaluation, configuring three different persona's in multiple cultural environments, in these perspectives, the students developed different perspectives and the archetypes behind the engagement with the product. Those archetypes related with the visual communication concept could work in different levels. After completing the different persona's using different tools to retrieve contemporaneous information, students highlighted the most important references in the persona's profile related with the different user perspectives.

The goal is to grasp the visual context, creating a more pleasant experience, a better effort co contextualize within defined perspectives. Those perspectives come from the persona study, after filtering the information, the working group will get a common structure, related with a specific unsolved situation in the persona's scenarios. The process gives awareness on scenarios built to summary components unattainable through other channels. Only an empowered systematization in the creative process can better output the results achieved during the design process.

The third filters focus on the emotional archetypes through Martins (2007) and Hartwell and Chen (2012) definition. Martins offers an attractive approach strategy in his book *The Emotional Value of Brands*, where the author presents the Carl Jung emotional archetypes (E.A) as support to define a brand personality. The Martins model, although not yet translated to English, offers a rich tonal range of associations delivering a pleasant didactic approach. Although this author and others, apply the concept into corporative brand meaning, his approach allows other ramifications to broader visual communication categorizations.

A design project always targets a product, physical or conceptual in his nature. As both a face and a function, archetypes can reveal how a brand shows up in the world, how it is motivated and what triggers it. Archetypes can facilitate the understanding of the brand and why it attracts certain customers (Hartwell & Chen, 2012, p. 9).

The archetypes work as strange attractors of consciousness. The brand attracts customers when the brand is congruent with an archetype that is either dominant or emerging in the consumer consciousness (Mark & Pearson, 2001, p. 155).

In the fourth filter student work the storytelling strand, constructing the narrative sequence and applying a Kurt Vonnegut shapes of stories perspective. The author shows graphically how to depict a narrative, mapping out the shapes of stories. With irreverence and perceptive insight the author draws two axes, along the "G -1 axis" of Good Fortune and Ill Fortune and the "B-E axis" of Beginning and Entropy, (Vonnegut, 2017).

The Kurt Vonnegut concept when applied as a tool allows the combination with images retrieved from different images banks, resulting in image sequences illustrating different narratives. Correlated with dramatic intensity, each student group work those narratives and test the Emotional archetypes and cultural context characterization.

The fifth phase focuses the message elaboration, student collect all the information rounded up from previous phases and determine recurring to Edward T. Hall presuppositions, the message design.

Students filter the information on a cultural context perspective, applying the concept presented by Edward T. Hall. The addressed approach in a communication project design must match and follow particular cultural settings retrieved from persona evaluation and cultural contextualization, following the Edward T. Hall definition of communication in lower and higher context.

Hall offers a systematic approach concerning the effectiveness of communication in cultures of low and high context. This approach is crucial for understanding communication and its extensions in the various forms of the message because the context as the vehicle of communication interferes in the message content and structure.

The context is an important way to deal with the enormous complexity of human transactions. Distributing context analysis in a graphic arrangement. Hall places the high context messages at one end and low-context messages in another extreme of a continuum.

A high-context communication or message is one in which most of the physical context information is present or previously internalized in the person, while there is very little explicitly in the message transmitted. In a low-context culture, the opposite is true. In a low-context culture, for example, twins who grew up together can communicate between them with the same effort than two lawyers in the courtroom during a trial.

This diagnostic method fosters learning transference. According with Findlay (2014) the concept of learning transfer is crucial when establishing that learning is also an effect. The ludic factor is the necessary motivation to increase self-efficiency, but also to transfer knowledge and learning to other contexts. The ability to transfer knowledge into other domains may only be possible at a meta-level, because the level of transformation that allows the motivation process to continue and intensify may be intrinsically vital to the acquisition of learning abilities. Based in this approach students developed their options focusing on questions related with project evaluation in the image strategy architecture, this should comprise several routes and cycles but display a certain level of accessibility for consumer assessment. Managing a high quantity of information in only one screen of information, students aim their developed skills in accessing a direct and non-cluttered interface.

The sixth phase, more related with the aesthetic properties concerns the graphic layouts. This phase encloses the final maps with the frames on the final output resolution. Involves applying symbolic information retrieved from the second diagnostic, tuned with the visual communication target.

The students design different levels of hierarchy, experiencing the flow between qualitative data and storytelling mockups, designing the different visual responses or alerts each one with different "dramatic" levels. A graphic evaluation enables a better design of the time and how certain visual responses work in the future communication framework.

The learning module comprises fifteen sessions, with the duration of the course (3 months). In The first two phases is crucial the student's involvement in working sessions composed of the technical and conceptual model construction and their discussion. In the first stage related to the Introduction and discussion, students work the diagnostic practice, through the persona method. Although general, the diagnostic practice will provide clues and a stronger argumentation for later development in each students group.

The first sessions that involve persona construction and cultural code, make use of cardboard sketching with function and the concepts architecture description. From those evaluations, students produce the first mockups. After this phase, the information gathered by the entire classroom is subject to analysis by each group. From this point forward, each group undergoes the second image diagnostic evaluation, this time focused on aesthetic elements, collecting information for each proposal. Each group will conduct the second phase of the project development till the final image proposal. The teacher can contribute on online and traditional classroom learning settings, given that the first part is more focused on traditional classroom activity and the second half more focused on online interaction.

5.2.1 Conclusion

To bring new insights to the classroom has several implicit challenges, the learning module must allow a contemporaneous view into some of the problematic present on diagnostic research. Through the proposed NEOD model, students can develop different solutions for the different phases allowing different project outputs, the restricted symbolic concepts gain a new relevance. Although not easy to incorporate distinct concepts in the proposed learning module the construction in a sequence of different phases allow students to experiment a planned project direction.

The Learning module must communicate an open assembly structure and must provide to students the layout of activities, fostering in them a critic insight and ludic perspective, distributing a proceeding instead of a formula. The learning module attempts to create a tool perspective in the different concepts and stages. Attempting to delay the responses through the creation of different filters, promoting in students a more organized working practice in visual assessment.

This module development is a contribution to overcome the preconceived idea in students that visual responses are all intuitively expressed. The module works the idea that these can result from a strategic and tactic analysis of information, producing solid results, even when based on a qualitative assessment.

Often as teachers we perceive that designers can't valorize too much fashion trends, but trends and their imagery, although constantly renewed, are the symbolic coating, the renewal skin of ancient renewed symbols. Is central to foster this perspective in students, to foster an updated visual literacy on the permanent changeable imagery patchwork that forms the image product.

5.3 Product and brand, design insights from myth dissemination

The following project description aimed in the development of a product, framed in how rumors and consequently myth play a role in a learning module design focused on product design development. When communicated crowdfunding platforms, a new product concept is just another project, outside and alone is a myth and holds a unique strength.

The main limitation in this LMD relates to students the knowledge of technological solutions to build a credible solution and the obtained results from the diagnostic phase.

The student feedback on a different way to interpret the "consumer" needs, what will happen when we as teachers change the project structure?

The experimental learning module design (L.M.D) focused on the product development solutions included a mixed strategy, with explicit and implicit levels. The module structure followed the DES method strategy.

The dramaturgical method applied was the "Dramaturgical E-learning Strategy (DES)" by Mödinger and Thissen (2005). Within DES, tasks are transformed into conscious and unconscious spheres of experience using a basic dramaturgical structure (i.e., exposition, confrontation, and solution), cryptic knowledge, and community (i.e., a social communicative context), *Figure 02*.

Figure 02

Structure of Dramaturgical E-learning Strategy (DES)

In the L.M.D perspective, the myth is a tool in finding new ways of "teasing" new product solutions in the consumer perception.

The L.M.D. included nine in-person sessions, with sessions of three hours each. The sessions were divided by; briefing presentation and discussion, scope of solutions (technological, digital and portable solutions), search empty areas through diagnosis (how to simplify a strategy and clarify concepts of solutions), prototype application (3D simulation), social media platform dissemination and feedback insights. The L.M.D. was developed in a mixed strategy, constituted by online and in-person sessions.

The diagnosis involved the use of persona method and was presented to student's concepts about the contemporary social and cultural structure, specifically about the concept of punishment of Sisyphus.

The development of this learning module was important to test how students would react to a design oriented towards consumer expectations but using a strategy where the rumor would serve in the leverage of expectations about a product that "could exist" attempts to perceive the impact perception of the perspective of what is a design project.

For the L.M.D. the project briefing started with the assumption that in the in neo-liberal logic, is possible to achieve the investment interest, even outside from direct networks of crowdfunding, through the use of a myth approach to product design.

When communicated in crowdfunding platforms, a new product concept is just another project, outside and alone is a myth and holds a unique strength. The student proposal should structure the work in four areas; the product proposal, the product as a solution, communication, and the dramaturgic strategy. The dramaturgic strategy should include rumor and propagation of information.

This concept was introduced regarding the need to reinterpret the standard notion of design, and each product is a new possibility, but also a new problem. The modern consumer is seduced with new "solution" products, supposedly developed to solve real problems but often unsolved questions generated by other products, which end up presenting more challenges to maintain and take care of causing enormous human wear. If a rumor is in the genesis of a product will it enter into the same cultural structure of consumption?

In the project briefing, students were asked to find new product solutions. Students started to identify the problem or "empty areas" in daily life situations. Those empty areas relate to space where consumers don't have a brand with the capacity to represent solutions and new concepts. Students started to define scenarios where a semi-technological product could bring or solve that space.

After that identification, students focused their efforts on the product solution, in the graphic simulation and how it could communicate fast and straightforward solutions. That aspect is determinant to amplify the myth, in the proposed solution but also in the applied structure. The new product concepts and brands trigger new associations, and in this perspective, the DES method works as a distributive concept through the L.M.D.

In 2016 the concept (post-truth), which according to the Oxford dictionary refers to denoting circumstances in which objective facts are less influential in shaping public opinion that appeals to emotion and personal belief, was widely spoken.

Although focusing on the power of myth and its possibilities applied to Design, the L.M.D, through it implicit and explicit structure, had also the purpose of helping students to differentiate between myth and rumor.

The project briefing resulted in four projects and from those, two stood out, one for its logic, the 4care, a badge that was meant to control the distance radius of anything or anyone relevant to the user, *Figure 03*.

Figure 03

4Care project concept developed by students

The second project, called “Swipe & charge” related to a system, which allowed the user through a sticker charge a battery, the charge would be obtained from the mouse friction against a contact surface, *Figure 04*.

Figure 04

Swipe & charge concept.

When students experienced this L.M.D. perspective, they were able to entangle the story within the product, instead of using only the narrative in an argumentation discussion on the project evaluation. In some of the project's students 'recovered' the product narrative obtained from a diagnosis phase to defend their proposal or to give a 'complete' image of their project. Therefore, the myth narrative "glued" the different elements in the project improving the student argumentation, *Figure 05*.

Figure 05

Myth, the "glue" of information.

Educational projects work hand in hand with the cultural and social trends of a certain period. There is always present, implicitly, in a project briefing a social and cultural perspective, what could be considered a consumer product culture. That perspective must be explained to students through a structure and not only by the L.M.D contents. Altering the structure provides a different reality in the learning experience and therefore new boundaries to reason the project implications.

Each project proposal, beyond the landing page, had their communication in an image social tool app, the discussion included memes or images of the product, after was retrieved statistical information from the project response, applied only in qualitative terms in the project, to ascertain the feedback or interest of the web. Students could determine the impact of short messages and images about the product and feel the real impact of their communication, though, created for a fake product.

Making visible to students that the base structure of their project development changed, helped them understand the critical challenges of working with new consumer cultures. The focus that deals in reaching different mindsets go beyond the use of new technology. Was noticeable that students developed faster insight solutions compared with standard methods. The use of dramaturgical structure allowed an overall consistency in the project. The workgroup achieved a successful post confrontation, making visible and making explicit the L.M.D implicit concepts on the structure of myth and the way it "glues" different and even incongruent elements of a narrative. That fact was made true when using the deception trick and therefore reviving a limbic framework full of instinct and emotions.

Confronted with the question if they would feel so engaged if they were asked to design a product concept that would contribute for users' daily life in a scenario at choice, students answered that probably they would take more time and effort to get to similar insights obtained from this strategy.

The statement of one of the students summarize one of the most interesting results of the project, related to the structure of a non-linear track "*...when someone asks us to design a solution, something that would be a valuable contribution, we try to apply our best... but in a good way, in this one, apart from the good there is also a tricky side, and that feels something recovered from childhood and somehow more natural and human..*"

5.3.1 Product and Brand Conclusion

The experimented LMD allows students to experience their work on implicit and explicit levels, the problem to solve but also the way they reason the structure applied in solving that particular question. There are still many prejudices on the use of a mixed strategy composed by design and the narrative most trivial tools such as the rumor on the project genesis. But what the experience and perception tell us is that these are the tools overlooked by companies and by designers. In the middle of the rubble of information, future designers must develop critical tools that allow them to detect trend fluctuations and test different strategies accordingly with those fluctuations. Structuring the knowledge over false truths is a paradigm and also an overlooked element of human history, the experience is a contribution in how to reverse this negative characteristic of human nature and society, giving students the experience of evaluating feedback oriented to product proposals that were designed keeping in mind a specific problem and that when changing the platform to conduct the problem the path changes accordingly with that platform. The project edified a structure over a “human” condition and therefore circumvent argumentation problems and project support, taking advantage of that “weakness” to reorient the design, agglutinates elements creates a shaped memory, facilitated by myth and a less ephemeral existence.

5.4 Visual Cartography Project

The Visual cartography project was developed in the context of the project Re-inhabiting the Barrio: Transformation and empowerment processes between universities-schools-societies through artistic practices. (“Re-habitar el barrio: Procesos de transformación y empoderamiento entre universidad-escuela-sociedad a través de prácticas artísticas.”) in the Joan Miró Educational Center, Palma de Mallorca, Balearic Islands, 2019.

The session with the children aged 5 to 7 years old, was previously tested with another group of students, collecting an evaluation of their reactions and nature of interaction with objects of graphic interpretation depicting specific neighborhoods.

The experience design aimed to trigger new behaviors through reflection, composition, and narration of images. Although, it was not possible to develop a pre-experience with a group of children, the pre-experience was conducted with students of the Master of Graphic Design, *Figure 06*.

Figure 06

Discovery session carried on with Master Students.

these group tested the playful aspects of construction and reasoning discovery processes triggered by connecting similar elements, **Figure 07**.

Figure 07

Previous Experience, neighborhood map, connections.

With the children of the School Joan Miró, the Visual Cartography workshop included the creation of collaborative visual narratives, and in various strata, their emotional mapping and location on location maps in the digital tool Google Maps.

The workshop included two sessions, on 28 and 29 May 2019. The 28 May session included the collection of drawings, identification, and organization of typologies and themes and the formation of groups of children. On May 29, the workshop focused on the synthesis of narrative routes, and the creation of collective narratives with the contribution of the several workgroups.

Graphic support material for the workshop included cardboard, pin, wool threads of different colors, and a glue gun. Note-taking support for the experience included photos and videos.

The project focused on Collecting drawings about the neighborhood and drawing connections. Each student produced one or more drawings of elements that caught their attention in their neighborhood. The children distributed the drawings in four cardboards, latter assembled in one large cardboard, with the help of pins of various colors, and threads of different colors, aided by the teachers, the children connected the drawings, drawn, joining similarities of represented elements. The wool threads of different colors for different types of objects displayed the various connections, *Figure 08*.

Figure 08

Children connecting similar elements found in different boards.

For discussion and reflection by the children, the teachers hung on a wall the connected cardboards, *Figure 09*.

Figure 09

Helping children connecting the four cardboards.

The visual impressions of the neighborhood reflected the perceptions of the students. Those graphic representations raised awareness among students about the possibilities of relating visual information, which, although “expressive,” offers a map of the neighborhood's valorization. Intervene these images through interaction with the materials that allowed the analysis of information through creative means and that allow the construction of your analog information network.

Students read images and listen carefully to their peer descriptions and managed the images as research elements of a map, classified and ordered the images according to similarity or representation. Students interpreted the structures through materials that bridge the visual elements. This organization fomented participative and interpretive dialogues about the depicted places as if they resulted from collective creation.

The teachers involved opened and closed the workshop, guided, contextualized the activity, and for research purpose, documented the workshop. They provided graphic support material and material to draw connections. They assisted in changes of perspective and analysis of information and its interpretation and discussed the creation of metanarratives (narratives created on the first interpretations). Supported on the correct group management in a collaborative work methodology

The teachers made available the card boards surface where students distributed the various drawings and connected the different colored threads, elements that appeared in the multiple representations (houses, depictions of people, animals, shops, etc.).

After displayed the overall panel (resulted from the assembled cardboards), each group consulted the map and surveyed the connections, selected several elements, and inserted the selection in their group interpretative drawing composition. These drawing compositions connected those elements into new narratives.

These “new narratives,” often of an ironic, comic, or critical character, provide a unity over the different perspectives of their paths.

The findings point that stories can work as shelters from the harsh realities of their neighborhood. The storytelling relieves the reality of these creations. To play is to create worlds, create heavens, shells.

We are more likely to retain family structures. Even when we represent the unfamiliar, familiar structures can carry out the conversion of what is unfamiliar in what is familiar.

Regarding the experiences developed, of a similar character, it is important to highlight that the drawings produced by the children in their neighborhood demonstrate that positive parents, community support and safe places play a huge role in their life (Meor Gheda & Sheikh Ilmi, 2019), safe places relate to neighborhood safety connected to outdoor play activities. Those may be best encouraged by improving different safety components (Sheikh Ilmi et al., 2018). Children need to spaces of dialog, need better social support services as they grow up (Zhou et al., 2019)

According with Affandi (2019) children's participation in place-making an urban environment are influenced to three attributes: (1) artworks as a mode of place-making for a positive emotional sense-of belonging, (2) active participatory of children in creating artworks could cultivate community bond and social skills, and (3) public sphere are spaces for children to exhibit their sense-of-attachment.

Around 1900 Aby Warburg was one of the who conceive children's drawings as a complex historical stratification of cultures and the different effects of anachronism.

According with Wittmann (2012) Warburg reconceptualized images as necessarily open compositions of temporally and geographically heterogeneous parts, as stages of revenant (returned) fragments of older form findings and symbolic languages.

In Warburg's understanding, drawing carries a double temporal trajectory: to the past as well as to the present. Thus, the historical moment as condensed in the artifact is conceived as a knot between synchrony and diachrony.

According to McEwan (2006) the question of "What does it mean to orient oneself in space?" was posed by Aby Warburg on the morning of the day on which he died, 26 October 1929, Warburg used the term "orientation" frequently in his research "Bilderwanderung," the journey of images. For him orienting himself in "Bilderwanderung," applied to "dig" for those thought processes that led people to a spatial grasp of orientation in the cosmos, similar to a geological map, which shows strata and routes of subterranean water courses that exist yet are invisible to the eye.

Social fragmentation divides create different containers separated by intervals. The designer can change the forms of public interaction, through connections on maps, showing feasibility through the communication of instructional solutions enables behavioral changes

Human behavior especially is not a product of a particular stimulus but of the whole image of the world in the mind of the behaving person (Boulding, 1956).

The creation of maps reinforces the message of intersection and encourages new behaviors, the approximation of different universes through mosaics, allows the creation of narratives and consequent mental maps.

The images give a sense of possibility, ascribing physical possibility to whatever the image displays by virtue of showing things as looking the relevant way (Gregory, 2019).

The designer is thus a process facilitator, Design strategies for 'raising awareness' can move people into a process of behavior change, these are the strategies that help people evaluate the choices they have made so far and place them in a new perspective (Ludden & Hekkert, 2014).

Vilém Flusser refers to the "conspiratorial" capabilities of the Designer, who covertly extends his "traps", (Flusser, 1993), In a positive sense, in the etymology of the Latin word its original meaning is read in the word *conspirare* "to agree, unite, plot," literally "to breathe together," (Harper, 2020a). To this designation we can add a manipulation function in the genesis of the word that was later used as a pharmaceutical expression and whose etymology of the word Latin, *manipulus*, se refere a "handful, sheaf, bundle," (Harper, 2020b).

Designers have an innate ability to "edit" the information, comparing it with the work of a film editor. Designers can select the best scenes (information and methods), creating a continuity, to constructively develop manipulation with a particular objective. In the specific case of the project described in the creation of narratives, that "unite" different areas of information, that relieve the cognitive load of disaggregated and not understood situations lived in their neighborhood.

Narratives play an important role in alleviating the cognitive burden, when they accompany an activity, (de Jong, 2010), Narratives allow children's to tap into their propensity to remember stories, helping them to make sense of the world (Didau, 2019).

In a logic of predominance of visual thought, from the polished digital of Byung -Chul Han (2017), it is essential to recover Warburg's "orientation in space" for an activity of "discovering" invisible relationships.

Co-creation triggers the interaction of multiple argumentations, the co-creation act "forces" the expression of different arguments. The *model of visual competences developed* by Marion G. Müller (2008) *defines visual competences as the ability to react appropriately.* The

More importantly, students attune to the design of visual texts they encounter outside the classroom, accordingly with Connors (2012) Suddenly movies, billboards, videogames, and magazine advertisements—that is, the kinds of texts with which they interact in their everyday lives—become fodder for analysis. As students view these texts anew, and as they experiment with a vocabulary that enables them to think and talk about images they become more critical consumers of visual texts. Most importantly, they develop a sense of appreciation for the way's different kinds of texts, visual as well as print, lend themselves to being read.

5.4.1 Visual Cartography Project Conclusion

The work carried out presents us two planes of information, one explicit through a connection of drawings in network and another that we could call implicit and that offers us information of a community, the expectations of a neighborhood through expressions and emotions narrated and written. The design of the action could change the forms of public interaction, through map connections, by showing the feasibility of connections through the communication of instructional solutions that in turn allowed feedback on behavioral changes. Social fragmentation divides and creates different containers separated by intervals. Human behavior, especially, is not the product of a particular stimulus, but of the complete image of the world in the mind of the person who behaves (Boulding, 1956)

Most of the works of author result from facts and realities experienced or observed in the environment and that have impacted with the identity of the author, prompting him to share his gaze with others. If the creative act involves life, the references of the self and the relationship with others, probably the collaborative process developed served to increase individual awareness and their collective exchange to foster a common vision about the neighborhood and its culture.

The elaboration of maps has reinforced the message of intersection and fostered new behaviors, the approximation of different universes through images, has allowed us to create narratives and consequent mental maps. These images give a sense of possibility, attributing physical possibility to whatever the image shows by virtue of evidencing things with a significative presence (Gregory, 2019).

The type of collective work produced, allows the reflexive development from multiple themes linked to the territories inhabited by those who participate in the experiences, fostering dialogue and collaborative work in constructing the work of multiple authorship. The linkage of places with personal experiences, unique and unrepeatable, gives space to the self-story that derives in the construction of artistic work from the life stories of those who participate (Montenegro González, 2019).

5.6 Learning Creative Strategy - An Itinerary Through a Mosaic of Visual Clues

The proposed strategy uses the gathering of visual references, followed by the reconstruction of the elements obtained (through contradiction and combination) and a final stage of critical reflection upon the visual results (Mosaics). The gather of visual references related with the specific product will serve two purposes: the creation of a Persona's Mosaic and the Mosaic of Tensions (based on the Persona's daily routine). The inclusion of the Persona's method in this strategy will provide the necessary clues to the Storytelling phase. The assemblage of the gathering in visual *tiles of information* will allow to extract a wide variety of visual clues. This will ease the storytelling, through the concept of *Synecetics, the stranger is made familiar and the familiar made strange*. By creating different stories, students' reason about product institutions and their cultural value. Moreover, this configuration in small *tiles* can be seen and interpreted without the barriers of verbal language, this way, students of different cultures and nationalities can work together with the same purpose. Each narrative discussed among the students will then originate new insights.

The proposed strategy works with two Mosaics, the Persona's (profile) Mosaic and the Mosaic of Tensions. Both are constituted by tiles of visual representations of concepts linked with the product and its consumer. When developing this kind of information' gather students must consider the "availability profile" that will determine the propensity to the product or service that the Persona will consume. The "availability profile" is the "fictional" Persona's willingness to interact with a specific product. This willingness is correlated with the rhythm of that Persona daily routine and spare time. This perception of time and how it is managed by the everyday consumer represented by the Persona, allow students to understand the consumers' daily needs, those essential to survive or to complement their life. The lack of time due to Persona's daily stress can also present exciting opportunities, for new products or services that can alleviate such tension. The visualization of these moments of calm *versus* tension can give clues and help students to understand the availability profile, focusing on *highlighting* moments of consuming propensity.

In the assemblage of the Mosaics, students will create a creative guidance of stories linked to the consumer environment. The French sociologist Pierre Bourdieu (1986, p. 100) stated that "the consumer helps to produce the product he consumes". Following this idea, the Persona will give clues that can change the perception, communication and orientation of a product.

In the classroom context, this strategy will consist in two sessions, of three hours each. The first involves the creation of the Persona's Mosaic, the second the Mosaic of Tensions and Storytelling. The Storytelling will result from the confrontation of the representations of concepts in the Mosaic of Tensions and with the Persona's. In this phase, students can create contextualized narratives that will give structure and literacy for the first drafts of the product communication.

In detail, the purposed creative strategy involves four phases of construction; in the Phase 1, students begin by defining the Persona's Mosaic with particular features of the person's life, retrieved from search engines and image database (name search, maps, trends, etc.), *Figure 10*.

Figure 10

Persona Phase 1.

In the Phase 2, still in the Persona's Mosaic, students will define the daily routine and stress peaks in it by using the textual description and colors related to different intensity peaks. Each area numbered (4) is filled with a gradient. The high levels of stress in a day are displayed in red and the low levels of stress in blue, *Figure 11*

Figure 11

Persona Phase 2.

In the Phase 3, students will obtain cohesive solutions from the Mosaic of Tensions. This mosaic constituted by a sequence of moments of their daily routine is composed by images that represent concepts of calm, interspersed with representations of tension in the Persona's life, *Figure 12*.

Figure 12

Persona Phase 3.

In the Phase 4, that portrays the Mosaic of Tensions, the students discover possible associations triggered by the contrasts in the sequence of the tiles, *Figure 13*.

Figure 13

Discovering new associations.

The associations resulting from the creation of Visual Storytelling in the Mosaic of Tensions will allow the development of cohesive answers anchored in the development of the Persona. The Persona represents in this stage a socio-cultural reference of the final consumer of the product, *Figure 14*.

Figure 14

One of the students' Mosaics.

5.6.1 An Itinerary Through a Mosaic of Visual Clues Conclusion

The purposed creative strategy offers possibilities, but the reasoning behind it requires a starting point, an anchor and an itinerary for further development of the project, in a nurturing perspective, the *breath of creativity*. Systems such IDS provide creative itineraries. However, they are not effective without a cultural anchoring. The Synectic technique, provides an attractive solution because it uses the mnemonic ability as a mirror of creativity and allow students to play in an exploratory approach with a cohesive focus.

Following a cultural anchor, the Visual Storytelling, also empower the immersion in the narration, and deepen the problem-solving reasoning. In this paper Visual Storytelling, is presented as a mechanism to foster intuitive creativity, through visual analogies and metaphors. The Persona's method, through visual clues based on the cultural and social context, will also contribute, providing a hypothetical scenario of the product's consumer. This way, Visual Storytelling based on tiles grouped with information will frame the field of action, give rise to new ideas and cohesive answers to the future development of the project. At the beginning of the project, students must consider collect and reflect on visual elements associated with the universe of consumption of a particular product or service. Thus, we should understand this, as a creative strategy where a collection of concepts are built at various levels of refinement.

The presented strategy also reinforces a Synectic's approach, in a way that *makes the relative strange and the strange familiar*. The creation and assemblage of the *tiles* will create visual clues that will orient the product communication design. In general, Storytelling when allowing different visual associations and interpretations, conducted and supported by image reasoning will contribute to foster visual culture and help students develop critical thinking.

5.7 Visual Diagnostic Exploratory Study

The strategy related with to the visual diagnostic exploratory study involved the collection of visual information with different attributes and applications. The concepts behind each of the Design Thinking phases of the strategy followed a perspective of conceptual filters.

According with(Kernbach & Svetina Nabergoj, 2018) By making the functions of visualization explicit in general and showcasing examples for each of the design thinking phases, design thinking practitioners and researchers are inspired to think of and make use of visualizations more consciously

Each phase results in a summary of information, which, when added to the summaries of the remaining phases, qualitatively allows the development of the communication context. The resulting communication follows the perspective that it is more than mere communication, presenting itself as a perspective of product use. The three phases involved the collection of information of a distinct nature, the strategy for the first phase uses image references. According to a previous article Silva (2014b).The phases involve the collection of visual information structured in three lines of force;

- Archetypal Guidance
- Product cultural code
- Customer journey

The archetypal orientation is formed by Images that form a constellation of references of archetypal images according to cultural and commercial identifiers. From the different configurations of symbolic attributes and reference tables, the Martins model (2006) offers several possibilities of associations between images and archetypes, providing a friendly didactic approach. The contextualization of cultural positioning follows the selection of emotional archetypes at different levels of intensity.

Cultural positioning results from cultural synonyms collected from emotional archetypes, surveyed in commercial online image services. In them, the students obtain the images, employing the identification of image tags.

In this strategy, students work the reasoning of images and the correlation of the concepts of the emotional archetypes. A systematic approach to visual research uses tools consistent with the design of visual communication, and students update visual literacy through the investigation of different cultural settings. According to (Lopez-Leon 2015), when developing visual literacy in design through visual reports, students report that unlike a written report, generating an image makes them reflect on the interpretation, stop for a moment to think, and sometimes even go back and corroborate information.

This perspective relates to the concept of inference, a conclusion reached on the basis of evidence and reasoning. The primary use on inference is that research creates ideas for design. According with Koskinen & Lee (2009) They vary in whether inspiration is enough, or whether they also see explanation and understanding as crucial elements of research. Secondary functions relate inference to decision-making and creating theory. The inspiration-oriented research tradition, Inspiration: Bringing Art to Design Research, plays down these functions, while the other two traditions, Explanation: Understanding Design through Experiments and Statistics and Interpretation: Induction and Fieldwork function in a scientific mind-set, linking new studies to tradition research, *Table 2*.

	Key Words	Models	Institutional grounding
Inspiration	Probes, design noir	Builds on art world metaphors and examples	Art worlds, professional design
Explanation	Design and emotion	Modeled after cognition and experimental psychology	HCI
Interpretation	Empathic design and sociological concepts.	Builds on sociological theory	Design research

Table 2 - Three theories in nutshell according (Koskinen & Lee, 2009).

This strategy aims to overcome some lack of structure in the introduction of the design project. The strategy allows for a more detailed approach to a consulting perspective, *Figure 15*.

Figure 15
Strategy phase 1

The Product Code is an evaluation based on the testimonials of product experience (or an associated generic product). This evaluation involves the collection of anonymous individual testimonies to which found recurrences and information patterns may result in a standard definition of the product. According to Rapaille (2008), the discovery happens when the structure is observed and not the content. We could illustrate this principle with an example of a story, West Side Story, whose "content" is different from that of Romeo and Juliet, but which tells the same story. The important thing is the structure of the story and the connection between the various elements.

The same applies to a sound melody, its structure is in the space between the notes, in the interval between one note and the next, these intervals constitute the rhythm. The key to understanding the true meanings behind our actions is to understand the structure.

In trying to understand why people act in specific ways or do certain things, we need to look beyond the content and enter the structure. In any situation, there are three distinct structures in action. The first is the biological structure, the DNA. However, each species is unique because the organization of its DNA - its structure - is unique. The following structure is culture.

All cultures have a language, an art, a habitat, a history; the way all these elements, contents, are organized, creates the unique identity of each culture. The final structure is the individual because each of us has a unique relationship with our family that shapes our mental scripts and creates our identity. We can start with the same content, but we end up developing different structures.

When reading the stories that the students tell in the discovery sessions, it is the structure, the most crucial element to retain. When working with a brand, for instance, of ice cream, it does not matter if people eat ice cream on the beach, at home, in the city park. What matters is the connection between the consumer and the ice cream, between the experience of eating the ice cream and the feelings evoked, the experience evoked is the structure of the consumer experience. At this stage, students collected five testimonials associated with the experience of the product, or associated product, compiled the experiences in a single document and carried out an analysis at the level of information standards, *Figure 16*.

Figure 16
Strategy, phase 2.

The third phase presents the dynamics of storytelling according to the logic of the customer journey. The Customer journey refers to the creation of a narrative of consumption for the intended product or service, in the creation of the narrative contexts are investigated associated with contemporary consumption behaviors making explicit information about the implicit (seduction) and explicit touchpoints consumption. Our overall experience interacting with any enterprise is never fully captured by the simple summation of separate experiences at different touchpoints. When it comes to customer touchpoint experience, across all different touchpoint modes as well as across all different touchpoint occurrences, the “whole” is profoundly more – and different – than the “sum of the parts (Dhebar, 2012).

From this analysis, we obtain information that synthesizes the logic of the consumption path, where the product can gain certain qualities or characteristics resulting from the consumer journey. Customer journeys are not only as a means to take the viewpoint of the customer but also to reach insight into their experiences (Følstad & Kvale, 2018), **Figure 17**.

Each of the phases connects to a summary of information presented in the form of an image; the first phase relates to dominant image concepts. The second phase refers to Concept Represented in two or three words and their image representation and the Third, to a story gist and Image mystical/easy culture narrative identification. These three summaries, in turn, give rise to a Visual Composition from the three phases, an assembly that brings together the concepts of the project, *Figure 18*.

Figure 18

Strategy map, overall view.

The Composition from the three phases would thus be based on the first phases of analysis and would produce a more effective approach in the communication of the developed product, *Figure 19*.

Figure 19

Students presenting their findings.

The example of the presented project refers to the communication of the entrepreneurship project entitled Natura Glamping, a project that emerged in 2015, localized in the Serra da Gardunha in Portugal. The project proposes tourist accommodation facilities in the open air that associating the contact with nature to the comfort of the housing, providing unique and diversified experiences, defending the Ecological concept, and Nature Tourism.

In the development of the visual diagnostic exploratory study, the student defined the archetypes that emphasized the discovery and enjoyment of "slow magic." The product code displayed the interior and exterior discovery, and the customer journey pointed out the pleasure of "slow magic," an experience of reality where fits the fantasy, identified by the reference to Peter Pan. In the following steps, the student would develop strategic solutions on Social media, using captivating images associated with a brief video teaser and allowing consumers to establish these associations. The sum of these associations results in an image composition that praises the experience of time and the discovery of Nature's "Slow Magic," consequently, this is the result of the development of the Natura Glamping product. communication code, *Figure 20*.

Figure 20

Student Joana Dias final example pane, due to the copyright of the images used, was purposely pixelated. The image located to the right shows the summary of the whole process.

When applying the visual diagnostic exploratory study, the students demonstrate difficulties at two levels. The first difficulty level encountered relates to the development of positioning of archetypes, according to the profile of positioning of the consumer. The second problem relates to the development of narratives, which are not forced by the final product from which unrealistic narratives result. These narratives must result from a "meeting" with consumer behaviors and forms familiar to potential consumers, in the channels where a product can seduce. The use of visual diagnostic strategy boosts competitiveness because it allows students to explore each stage individually and in-depth, the concepts related to their communication strategy without precipitating results. Exploration through an investigation of visual rhetoric by increasing the student's visual literacy about the subject within a cultural framework allows them to achieve more effectively innovative design solutions.

5.7.1 Visual Diagnostic Exploratory Study Conclusion

At the level of the effectiveness of the visual diagnostic exploratory study, it can guide creativity solutions delimited by three perspectives, archetypes, product cultural code, and customer journey. These three levels are operated as information filters and allow for greater security in the project's argumentation and safety in the development of the project, to some extent alleviate the "cognitive load" of the challenge presented by the project.

The difficulties experienced in the positioning of the archetypes happen, students show some problems in understanding the perspective of the potential consumer, in this sense, it is essential to include in the student's perception, a standpoint of consumer behaviors and product potentiality. In the form of a metaphor, the designer should be a constant advocate of the product, and from this, they were able to wield visual arguments from different contexts that "defend" the product.

The difficulties felt in the creation of customer narratives are associated with difficulty in externalizing an intuitive knowledge about consumer practices and consumer vehicles. The students know these consumption channels intimately, but because they do not consider them "prestigious," they do not externalize them. These channels are the social platforms that students use everyday life, characterized by the dominant role of the image.

The visual diagnostic exploratory study allows students to think with images more consciously by drawing attention to the need for culturally delimited visual literacy. In this way, it reinforces a responsibility that future designers must have when developing communication solutions for products and services. The image is not merely a graphic content without connection with real-life because it is, after all, due to the behaviors it communicates, the agent that triggers a series of interactions with reality.

5.8 Exploring climate change through LSP - A Learning Experience

The learning experience followed a strategy of constructionism. For Papert & Harel (1991) the simplest definition of constructionism evokes the idea of learning-by-making. The example of someone assembling Legos like a painter is a description of an activity but evokes a “way” of doing through the use of metaphors. For Maxwell (2006) community and constructionism go hand in hand. Constructionism allows two perspectives; one more related to the actual physical experience and staying close to the object can do as well as those who prefer a more analytic formal style.

The briefing that supported the development of the learning experience comprised three phases. The first phase, that took place in one session with a duration of three hours, focused on the theme of climate change. The second phase that took place in two sessions, with a length of six hours included the development of the strategy using the LSP, followed by the extraction and discovery of information. The third phase that took place in two sessions, with a duration of six hours involved the development of proposals. In the second phase, after presented the project briefing, each student received a small bag containing fourteen pieces. Students carried out two exercises, repeated twice, before the collective discovery exercise. Firstly, based on an image of a pre-developed montage, the students were asked to assemble the construction corresponding to the image, the students had five minutes to assemble the construction. They were then asked to develop a composition on their understanding of climate change within ten minutes. At the discovery session, now collectively, students developed a construction on the question: “How to increase the psychological impact of climate change?” according to the assumption of Norgaard (2011) about the psychological impact of climate change, *Figure 21*. Each of the people involved in an LSP session puts in place a personal creativity strand. For Stierand & Dorfler, (2014) personal creativity relates to the ability to (re) interpret the experience of the objective world into ideas that are original and useful. Intuition plays a significant role in the dynamics between creativity and judgment of a new idea. Intuition can also be understood as direct knowledge.

Figure 21

Students engaged in the final composition.

The composition made by the student's highlights domains of implicit knowledge made explicit by the tangible experience of externalization with the LSP. The students analyzed and identified the structural elements presented in the composition. In the final LSP montage assembly, at the structural level, it is evident that the elements are arranged in a row as if it were a moving shape. An item illustrative of the pollution, represented by the green wires connects the different "sections" of the montage, **Figure 22**.

It is of interest to emphasize the "direction" of the composition, student described as a representation of the sea, in one end and the other a representation of the more developed societies. The composition expressed implicitly in its shape, illustrates a direction towards the more advanced societies, **Figure 22**.

Figure 22

LSP Final composition overview.

In the identification of structures, resulting from the discovery session, students relate the structure “3” to Nature. This identification is very interesting because the "representation" of Nature (made with green Lego bricks) doesn't occur throughout the composition, it is particularized and designated as a structure, within the sequence, composed of more groups overall distinguished by different color groups, *Figure 23*.

The most interesting of this information, resulting from the discovery session is the identification of Nature as a commodity. According to Huang (2019) commodities are things of value and uniform quality, this homogenous nature of commodity quality provides possibility for exchange and distribution. Commodities are uniform to the extent that they are considered to be equivalent and interchangeable to those of other producers. Commodities are things of value that are traded in large quantities. Commodities in turn are transformed into different consumer products with different commercial placements.

Structures	
Structure 1	Pollution stain
Structure 2	Pollution
Structure 3	Nature
Structure 4	Society
Structure 5	Society
Structure 6	High developed societies
Connector	Pollution

Figure 23

Montage identification with structures identified.

This question is of great interest in understanding a guideline for a concept according to the perspective of Clotaire Rapaille and Timothy Morton. Although controversial, the perspective of Nature as a commodity allows us to envision innovative solutions at the level of speculative design, solutions that include product development from an evolutionary and non-sustainable perspective and to understand how the narratives associated with these products could act at the level preparation of consumer practices.

The effectiveness of this strategy is made explicit by the students' findings through the analysis of the composition structure developed in LSP. Discovering very organized ways of understanding processes and phenomena that would otherwise be difficult to make explicit, the discovery session puts in evidence that there is a significant source of preexisting intuitive information latent in students involved in the learning experience according to decision-making processes (Kaufman et al., 2010; Lieberman, 2000)

The sketches developed by students explore the strand of consumer product, where an evolutionary perspective is present where artificiality is framed in a logic of comfort reducing the emphasis on productivity logic, *Figure 24*.

Figure 24

(Left) Gabriela Silva, hanging garden. (Right) Luisa Varela, self-powered sound flower pot.

Regarding this study, the authors would like to thank the collaboration of the students from the course of Information Design 4d, Master of Graphic Design, course of the Association Master between the School of Applied Arts of the Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco and the Faculty of Architecture of the University of Lisbon, 2nd semester of the academic year of 2018/19.

5.8.1 Exploring Climate Changes Conclusions

Although the limits of the experience carried out, regarding the subject/ question explored in learning experience “How to increase the psychological impact of climate change?” the perspective of Nature as a commodity and in this specific case, through solutions that employ Nature “elements” as consumer products allows to create a connection of positive dependence on Nature. Achieved through an appropriation that assumes the artificiality of design solutions.

When developing speculative solutions such as the use of energy from Nature, where plants can be "used" as an aesthetic element of comfort, compatible with the perspective of Timothy Morton, a perspective of consumer products also occurs. That perspective allows a better psychological impact, both positive and active, consistent with the understanding of an “evolutionary” connection with Nature according to the perspective of Clotilde Rapaille.

The formation of this concept constituted by an evolutionary relationship with the nature and comfort of a consumer product that, although artificial is in its artificiality an appropriation of Nature, allows several possibilities in terms of the development of design solutions and is useful to the level of attraction of consumption.

We ask, as a result of this learning experience, if two-dimensional visual cultural artifacts do not delimit visual reasoning, if the reasoning limitations are the result of an operational limitation felt by students in the quality of their visual representations. In those representations, students seem to be limited in understanding the real extensions and repercussions of their discoveries.

The LSP offered a more tangible strategy, enabling a stronger engagement with the research subject and allowing richer discovery sessions. As a strategy, it offers interesting solutions in testing perceptions and logic that are not explicit and also empowers intuitive insights from implicit learning experiences. This learning experience will be reinforced with further studies of qualitative nature to "reinforce" the strategy of tangible discovery, associated to the exploration of concepts in a perspective of speculative design focused on the issue of climate change.

5.9 Visual Storytelling - Creative Strategy of Visual Clues

The visual exploration strategy tested in a learning module, focused on the introduction of a digital design project on the communication of an agro food product, included the following five mixed learning sessions (classroom and online) each with the duration of 3 hours.

- Experimental session physical exploration
- Theoretical session
- Development
- Development, discussion and presentation (first refinement)
- Development, discussion and presentation (second refinement)

In the Experimental Session with the bee pollen product, the students were able to taste the product and mix these products with other available food products (provided by the teacher) to test their compatibility. Then followed a Theoretical Session on Carl Jung's emotional archetypes and archetypal images forms in contemporary culture. In the visual exploratory sessions (Development Sessions), which took place during three sessions were organized so that in the first session students could collect images of the archetype that had been distributed to them and create their first associations and narratives. In the second and third sessions, students continued the visual exploration, but also discussed their findings and present them to the group of students in a two-round refinement.

In the Development Sessions an Archetypal Map containing a table of archetypal correspondences according to Kent Wertime (2002) and Archetypal Image Association Prism adapted from Woodside, Sood and Miller (2008), was made available to the students. The table adapted from Kent Wertime provides gist's of stories for twelve archetypes together with examples of brands that explicitly or implicitly communicate these archetypes.

The Archetypal Image Association Prism adapted from the “Brand enabling archetype enactment by consumer” from Woodside, Sood and Miller, see **Figure 25**, emphasizes the importance of archetypes in deepening the meaning-making of classic narratives applied to marketing and consumer psychology. Arrow 1 represents the proposition that the predominantly unconscious desire to realize archetype leads consumers to act. Arrow 2 proposes that dramaturgical representations reflect one or more archetypes. Arrow 3 reflects the proposition that the archetype produced by the communication professional in a brand dramaturgy must correspond to the archetypal urges, mainly or totally unconscious, of the intended client. Arrows 4, 5, and 6 illustrate that the staging of a story by consumers, their retrospective storytelling reflect one or more archetypes; the same proposal applies to the brand narrative developed by the author of the brand communication.

However, Woodside, Sood and Miller, citing an earlier paper (2006), caution that researchers should not be arrogant and vain in believing that their interpretations of consumer story reports are necessarily accurate, complete, or the only ones applicable to the interpretation of the relevance of specific archetypes.

Figure 25

Summarized information from the “Brand enabling archetype enactment by consumer”, retrieved from the authors Woodside, Sood, Miller [15] - Figure 3.

In the prism presented to the students an adaptation was developed to the initial diagram of Woodside, Sood, Miller (2008), the arrows were dubbed phases, in order to experience a phasing of the information and to try another operability in the conceptual tool. The proposed strategy sought to understand how the representation of the archetypal image would provide clues to the logic of the product. This logic would be based on a dramaturgy representative of a real emotional experience, *Figure 26*.

Figure 26

The Archetypal Image Association Prism resulted from the adapted structure from the authors Woodside, Sood, Miller [15], distributed to students contained image references, which due to copyright issues cannot be reproduced in this document.

Although Woodside, Sood and Miller had already referred to the Wertime table in their 2008 paper, the proposed strategy in this paper tested how these two “tools” could work together in the context of a digital design.

The Archetypal Images Schematic Working Map included three steps, a framework with the categorization of archetypes followed by an archetypal association prism and a diagram of associations resulting from the archetype association prism.

In order to complete the information needed to create the Archetypal Image Association Prism students worked with images collected on the Getty Images Bank. This image bank, although commercial, has a rich indexation attributed to the images, allows correlating concepts and, thus, to evaluate the cultural and commercial classifications of images.

The third phase presented in the schematic represents the extrapolation of information to a sketch, an approximate idea of the actual product using the elements resulting from the archetype association prism, **Figure 27**.

Archetypal Images Schematic Working Map

I - 12 archetypes map according with Wertheim (2002)

Archetype	Storyline	Brand examples
Ultimate Strength	When an obstacle is there, it must be overcome; strength must be proven in one.	Tropic, "It takes a beating and keeps going. That's the ultimate strength brand message."
The Hero	Power of action, linked with the possibility of adventure.	Alcoa by Charles Erwin Myers
The Hero	The Hero's journey and victory of journey and transformation.	Michael Jordan in Nike shoes, Joe Montana and Mr. Coffee, Power Pull Golf, Forest Gump
The Archetype	Universal message of attraction and attraction of one to the other.	Procter and Gamble, Howard Stern, Jerry Springer, Oakland Raiders, The Godfather, Harley Davidson
The Creator	Creative imagination and the power of imagination, originality, and self.	Coca Cola, The real thing, Nike, Disney, Alcoa
The Change Master	Transformation, self improvement, and self-empowerment.	Cartier, without eyes for women, Gilette's Mach 2, Razor, Porsche 911
The Powerbroker	Authority, influence and dominance—the world belongs to me—the best—the number one.	Chrysler, E.F. Rutzler, Bill Gates, Microsoft
The Altruist	Experiences, advice and heritage, staying the best of times.	Levi's, Die, Alan Kardec
The Specialist	Trust, quality, and reassurance.	Coca Cola and "Real" Ice Cream with bag of 12 TV commercial, L'Oréal, Long Island, Chevrolet
The Mother of Godheads	Family, nourishment, and motherly warmth.	Just Juice, Honey Soap, Singapore Change Juice, Aunt Jemima, Fairy (dishwasher), White of the Seal, Snow White
The Little Fish	Humor, uncertainty, and the element of surprise.	Domino's, Marmite, Earl Simpson, Pee Wee's Big Adventure
The Enigma	Mystery, suspense, and uncertainty.	Adventure, Spangolito, SuperHero, Domo, Alcoa, Coca-Cola, Frost, Top, Oak

Figure 27

Archetypal Images Schematic Working Map distributed to the students.

The group of twenty students was divided into 10 groups and each group developed an archetype from the table of archetypal correspondences according to Kent Wertheim . Each group had the challenge of working the original bee pollen product, developing a consumer and communication solution. In this way, the use of archetypal images would produce an emotional differentiation of perspectives of consumption and communication.

The strategy worked a sequence of divergent thinking followed by convergent thinking. According to Bowers (2012), the problem-solving process diverges and converges, expands and contracts. Divergence is the process of identifying, creating, and developing various ways to solve a problem. Convergence is the process of selecting and developing concepts of the multiple objectives developed at the beginning of the project.

In the learning phase, the process diverges and expands as the information is gathered, then contracts as the information is analyzed at an identification phase. The process then expands again into the generation of ideas as multiple concepts are developed and contracted in the evaluation phase, where a single concept is refined and implemented. In the proposed strategy, in the phases of divergent thinking regarding the learning and generation of ideas, occurs an expansion shaped by the cultural context characteristics represented by the archetypal images.

The application of the proposed creative strategy resulted in an understanding of archetypal images as a constructive element in exploratory diagnostic studies that support the development of a design project.

By dividing the work process into several phases, the students detailed each step and reflected on the action value of the archetypes. The development of an exploratory reflection phase allowed students to develop a phased argumentation of the proposed solutions. When the solution does not work, the problem may be associated within the developed narrative, with a poorly constructed sequence, constituted of moments of anti-climax, followed by climax moment where the product should appear as a credible solution. Students worked narrative logics based on patterns of action, represented by archetypal images.

A simple trend research does not offer a complete sampling, if anything, it can offer clues, 'arboretic' structures, but stripped of a narrative. Beyond the narrative that results from the Archetypal Image Association Prism, the intensity of the narratives is also "worked" through exposure to other colleagues and thus there is a co-production of value in the project.

According to Mootee (2013), growth-oriented narratives help extract emotional inputs and responses from stakeholders and can be used to instill optimism in the organization or reveal anxieties about the future. A limit-seeking strategy is used, according to Jones (1992) to find limits within which acceptable solutions, the tested creative strategy follows the principles of incremental search, simulation and limit search rather than acceptable or unique acceptable values. The students had the opportunity to reorganize the support tool of the Schematic Work Map of Archetypal Images in their proposals, as can be seen in the example portrayed in *Figure 28*.

Figure 28

Nigma Panel - Polen in tea, exploratory work on the Archetypal Map. Panel of students Marco Martins and Marco Moreira.

5.9.1 Visual Storytelling - Creative Strategy of Visual Clues Conclusion

According to the objectives defined in the present paper, the use of an table of archetypal correspondences according to Kent Wertime of Carl Jung's emotional archetypes and a Archetypal Image Association Prism, adapted from Woodside, Sood and Miller [15] for the development of an exploratory work on the concept of archetypes was successful, although there have been some difficulties in constructing a narrative using only a sequence of images, it is worth noting the difficulty felt by the students in the construction of moments of anti-climax and climax.

When students used with the Schematic Work Map of Archetypal Images a bank of commercial images, as a support tool, they understood the importance of cultural indexing of images and how that indexation relates with the emotional archetypes.

The Archetypal Map was effective as support tool. It allowed students to test different associations, the coherence of the elements, and the reverberation of the archetype in the narrative and the proposed product experience.

By using the concept of archetypal images as a tool for generating ideas, students were able to understand the possibilities of using the concept as a tool, but it was necessary to include a small clarification session to reinforce the perspective of the emotional archetypes as patterns of action, in Institutions. The term "Institutions" applied refers to the sociological meaning commonly applied to customs, or behavior patterns.

With regard to the hypothesis presented concerning the concept of archetypal images as a creative tool and related to their ability to improve the visibility and adequacy of ideas arising from a work of generating ideas, the concept of archetypal images has great possibilities in terms of application in exploratory studies. It becomes clearer for students the possibilities of these "Institutions" in structuring narratives and contextualizing the visual exploration.

The use of the proposed creative strategy is validated as a support tool in reinforcing the diagnostic practice of visual exploratory studies as support for design projects.

The development of this exploratory study allowed the students to develop a phased argumentation supported by the narrative logic, from the exploratory work. The intensity and coherence of these narratives were "worked" through the presentation and dialog to other colleagues thus creating a co-production of value in the project.

5.10 Innovation in Traditional Productive Sectors - Visual Curation in Design

Exploratory studies can be part of larger strategies in order to guide the creative process. The REINOVA project, in its methodological proposal, present the necessary conditions for the implementation of a new international service that promotes networking, the creation of innovative companies with high potential and the reindustrialization of existing companies, increasing the competitiveness and growth of the sector agri-food. The specialization in this sector and the focus on niche strategies are innovations of the project, as well as the international character of the service implementation, with the sharing of the value chain. The good practice resulting from the project will serve as the basis for the definition of a collective cross-border strategy of the International partners, which consolidates the innovation ecosystem created and enhances the appreciation of the geographical origin of the new products, *Figure 29*.

Figure 29

Methodological proposal REINOVA project. ©IDNET Portugal 2020

The Project design component included the diagnostic strategy, Visual Communication Diagnostic Methodology (VCDM's), with the acronym in Portuguese of ME.DI.CO., That word in Portuguese, use the same letters, from the word “doctor” and works as a metaphor for communicating its purpose as a tool a project sequence, *Figure 30*.

Figure 30

VCDM's position in the Design Project cycle.

This strategy supports the development of Communication Design solutions. After developing the diagnostic study, the design team presented to entrepreneurs the results through imageboards and observed their reactions, in specific how the diagnostic results inferred about the development of the product in terms of its consumption context.

The strategy related with the Visual Communication Diagnostic Methodology (VCDM) involved the collection of visual information with different attributes and applications. The concepts behind each of the phases of the strategy followed a perspective of conceptual filters. Each phase results in a summary of information, which, when added to the summaries of the remaining phases, qualitatively allows the development of the communication context.

The VCDM as the name suggests, consists of making a diagnosis of the product to find a way to solve the problem. So, this tool starts by defining the emotional archetypes that most show this collective unconscious.

According to Carl Jung (2014), within the Collective Unconscious, there are psychic or archetypal structures. These archetypes are forms without their content that serve to organize or indicate psychological material. As he says, archetypes are primordial images, because they often correspond to mythological themes that reappear in popular tales or legends.

"Archetypes are not only impregnations of typical, regularly repeated experiences, but also behave empirically as forces or tendencies to repeat the same experiences. Each time an archetype appears in a dream, in fantasy or in life, it brings with it a specific "influence" or force that gives it a numinous and fascinating effect or impels action"(Jung et al., 2014).

José Martins (2007) states that emotional archetypes are common patterns throughout human culture, and perceived as states of mind or ways of understanding the world, directly linked to motivations and purchasing preferences.

The archetypal orientation is formed by Images that form a constellation of references of archetypal images according to cultural and commercial identifiers. From the different configurations of symbolic attributes and reference tables, the Martins model (2007) offers several possibilities of associations between images and archetypes, providing a nice didactic approach. The contextualization of cultural positioning follows the selection of emotional archetypes at different levels of intensity. Cultural positioning is achieved through cultural synonyms of the selected emotional archetypes, surveyed in commercial online image services, by means of the identification of image tags. "Purchasing motivations are related to individual needs, beliefs, and desires. The preference is aroused by images that are in the collective unconscious of people." (Martins, 2007).

That is, the purchase motivation is related to personal needs and desires, and brand preference is associated with the feeling present in the collective imagination, thus, occurs an association with the brand image. If a brand only attracts its consumers to satisfy their personal needs, its margin of progression in the market is limited, but if the brand has an archetypal definition of the product it sells, the possibilities of expanding the market and increasing its sales grow dramatically, *Figure 31*.

Figure 31

Choice and classification by the degree of importance, the emotional archetypes for the Tayousei brand, designed for the company Zé dos Caracóis, created by the authors.

This method is useful for considering brand objectives, desires, or limitations, perceiving consumers, to help guide decisions about a service or product. For each product, results in more than one persona, but only one should be the primary focus for the design. The persona method also helps to avoid some common design pitfalls, which can determine the failure of a product in its design, *Figure 33*.

PERSONA

Saul

30 years old, Translator in a website company.
From Brazil, recently living in Berlin, Germany.

He likes new realities, being a very cheerful and full of life. He loves to feel the possibilities that life can give him. He has a refined taste, as he has always been used to well-seasoned meats, so he is not afraid to try new, different things.

She loves to go to places that resemble other places in the world, good music and the opportunity to wear different clothes.

He lives alone and loves it, as well as likes to make new friends and the diversity that the city offers.

The possibility of going after work, where everyone goes, and being able to eat something that is not from there, fills it. This fusion between ancestral knowledge and technological innovation.

In this city you feel your spirit complete and free. He fought hard to get what he has today, so he lives happily and fulfilled. He sees himself as a fighter and a winner.

Figure 33

Tayousei persona method.

TAYOUSEI

たようせい

Once defined the personas, we should focus on just one, idealizing their day-to-day life, and then transposed into a graph entitled consumer decision journey, where we determine, through tools such as Google maps, the points of contact between the consumer and the brand.

There are several models to map the consumer's decision journey. The McKinsey model (Court et al., 2009) is one of them and involves the mapping of 5 steps:

- Consideration: This is the stage in which the consumer recognizes having a need and seeks information. It is common to resort mainly to search engines, the website of the brands you are considering, social networks, and forums.
- Evaluation: When evaluating existing alternatives, several studies indicate that consumers trust consumers' reviews much more than descriptions resulting from the company. In this phase, influencers (bloggers, friends, experts, etc.) have an essential role.
- Purchase: The purchase process is increasingly omnichannel, and there is a need to understand which channels the consumer selects to convert.
- Experience: After purchase, many consumers share their experiences with the brand/product/service through social networks.
- Loyalty: This is the point where the experience with the brand can contribute to customer loyalty, and here, applications in certain areas can make a difference, adding value to the customer and ensuring the continuity of the experience.

This mapping is beneficial to understand:

- Actions: What is the consumer doing at each stage? What activities are needed to move on to the next step? What kind of tactical operations can we implement (discounts, vouchers, etc.)?
- Motivations: Why is the consumer motivated to move to the next phase? What emotions are you feeling? Which touchpoints can be activated?
- Questions: What are the uncertainties that are preventing the consumer from moving to the next step?
- Obstacles: What structural barriers, costs, difficulties are retaining the consumer at a given stage?

The purpose of this mapping, **Figure 34**, is to define the various stages in the process, indicators and metrics so that it is possible to integrate offline and online strategies in the communication plan, creating, if necessary, touchpoints.

Figure 34

Consumer Decision Journey, designed for the Tayousei brand, by the company Zé dos Caracóis, created by the authors.

Involve the consumer in a story is an excellent strategy to captivate him and to guarantee a smooth interaction.

The storytelling technique enables to transpose the company's vision and its purposes into a communication plan, using narrative as a tool. This narrative must be attractive and accessible in order to be timeless in a harmonious and emotional way.

As Mootee (2013) suggests, the storytelling narrative must follow the following councils: It must be participatory: If we involve a lot of people in the narrative, or if your exposure goes through social networks where people interact, or if we still collect personal feedback information from employees, we must ensure that people feel part of the story. That these persons feel that history is familiar to them.

The story must be attractive: The platform conveying the story can make it a success or a failure. To make the message attractive, we must transpose the listeners to other places, experiences, spaces.

It must involve structure: In storytelling, the narrative serves to organize the information in a logical structure that must be followed, with beginning, middle and end. Because the narrator and the audience know this structure, they can focus on the content of the story. When content flows, a good storyteller can present challenges and complex information in a more precise and more familiar format to the audience.

It must be performative: When telling a story, efficient oratory expression involves the listener. A compelling narrator conveys the words alive, using dramatic techniques such as body language, tone, rhythm and the search for the right moment.

It must be tangible: People like things they can see and touch. Prototypes help us to be able to convey an idea tangibly, expressing the company's strategic intentions, chaining the way forward towards something concrete.

It should be fun: The narrative should be interactive just like the games, giving the listener the chance to understand the story as a whole, in a personal and interactive way. These "serious games" provide the possibility to explore and live the roles, tasks, and relationships within a system defined by rules within an already understood context.

It must be realistic: The narrative must be tangent to reality. Although the listener knows that it is a fiction, he must be able to identify its applicability. Then, the narrative must include a vision of the future and a possible growth that is beyond the reach of the listener, maintaining a plausible basis of being reasonable. Only then can the story inspire and stimulate, providing the necessary information to guide the listener. This whole process, if well accomplished, is able to diagnose the problem that the product has to answer, being an essential motto for defining the positioning of the brand or product.

At the end of the diagnosis, the entrepreneur in the discussion with the design team understood the new logics provided by the product narrative creation, *Figure 35*.

Figure 35

Tayousei trend board.

The narrative resulted from creating sequences and logics from the diagnosis image boards, that displayed a curation of visual information about the product. In the discussion meeting that lasted about two hours, the Design team and the entrepreneur constructed together a "discovery session" through images of multi-layered storied nature of experience and scenarios. According to a previous study (José Silva et al., 2018) image maps allow the creation of narratives suggested by constant comparison in image maps arranged in mosaic.

According to Winifred (Winifred, 2017) Designers can use maps to curate and synthesize their observations, mapmaking include three basic activities: capture, curation, and analysis. The complexity and amount of data, nowadays available, makes curation more difficult. This means translating data collected through different means into legible output, maps and mapping can be a mean to curate information.

The resulting communication follows the perspective that it is more than mere communication, presenting itself as a perspective of product use. The three phases involved the collection of information of a distinct nature, the strategy for the first phase uses image references. According to a previous article Silva (2014b).The phases involve the collection of visual information structured to filter information according to the project subject.

In this research the designers worked the reasoning of the image and the correlation of the concepts of the emotional archetypes. Systematic approach to visual research, uses tools consistent with the design of visual communication and designers update the visual literacy through the investigation of different cultural settings. According to Lopez Leon (Leon, 2015) referring an experience developed with design students, when developing visual literacy in design through visual reports, students report that unlike a written report, generating an image make them reflect on the interpretation, stop for a moment to think and sometimes, even go back and corroborate information.

Also, the VCDM aims to overcome some lack of structure in the introduction of the design project. The strategy allows for a more detailed approach to a consulting perspective

The VCDM allowed entrepreneurs, in a short time, to build scenarios, logics, and consumer narratives. These narratives must result from a "meeting" with consumer behaviors and forms familiar to potential consumers, in the channels where a product can seduce. The VCDM values two ways, on the one hand, it allows the sustained development of the strategies in the Design project. On the other hand, it will enable to enhance the curation and output of images associated with the project. Visual presentation extends the cognitive ability of humans to some extent, *Figure 36*.

Figure 36

VCDM's sequence.

Visualizations are regarded as way to relieve the cognitive burden and speed up processing according with (Scaife & Rogers, 1996), the visual presentations reduce search efforts, enhancing recognition of patterns (Card et al., 1999). The VCDM Images boards may represent a strategy in alleviating the cognitive load. Finding ways to reduce extraneous cognitive load may be an avenue to improving creative thinking (Redifer et al., 2019).

5.10.1 Innovation in Traditional Productive Sectors - Visual Curation in Design Conclusion

After building consumer narratives with the help of image boards, entrepreneurs were able to understand and internalize the Design solutions proposed for the project in a more fluid way. Triggering better reasonings in the final design proposals and easily justifying the why, becoming ambassadors for the strategies adopted. At the level of the effectiveness of the VCDM, it can guide creativity solutions delimited by three perspectives, archetypes, product cultural code, and customer journey. These three levels work as information filters and allow a greater security in the project's argumentation and safety in the development of the project, to some extent alleviate the "cognitive load" of the challenge presented by the project. The design project can value VCDM in two ways. On one hand, it allows the sustained development of the strategies in the design project, on the other hand, it allows to enhance the curation and output of images associated with the project. It fosters the argumentation of both designers and entrepreneurs in the communication and even in the product discovery.

5.11 Exploratory Assessment Conclusion

To bring new insights to the classroom has several implicit challenges, the learning module must allow a contemporaneous view into some of the problems present in diagnostic research. Through exploratory models, students can develop different solutions for the different phases allowing different project outputs, the restricted symbolic concepts gain new relevance. The Learning module must communicate an open assembly structure and provide to students the layout of activities, fostering a critical insight and ludic perspective, distributing a proceeding instead of a formula.

The learning module attempts to create a tool perspective in the different concepts and stages. The tested modules contribute to overcoming the preconceived idea in students that visual responses are all intuitively expressed.

Structuring the knowledge over false truths is a paradigm. It gives students the experience of evaluating feedback oriented to product proposals designed, keeping in mind a specific problem. When changing the platform to conduct the problem, the path changes accordingly with that platform.

Strategies such as the Diagnostic Models, although pluralist, have all in common a sequential nature. Can incorporate different filters of information, but their core goal is to provide a base of assessment that can "orient" and "nurture" the project conduction, providing creative itineraries in visual cultural frameworks.

In general, Storytelling, when allowing different visual associations and interpretations, conducted and supported by image reasoning, will foster visual culture and help students develop critical thinking.

The visual diagnostic exploratory study allows students to think with images more consciously by drawing attention to the need for culturally delimited visual literacy.

The next subchapter presents the final considerations with the research dissemination and future research avenues triggered by the present research.

6 FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The present research aimed to develop exploratory studies, on the basis of a project of Digital Design in the context of teaching - learning and aimed to focus some problems observed at the beginning of a design project in the field of diagnostic studies, systematization, visual literacy and argumentation. The study drew the following conclusions, considering the following general and specific objectives:

Regarding the General Research Objectives:

- In creating a contribution to the teaching of design on the issue of visual literacy based on cultural references.

The research contributed new insights to the Design learning experience presenting several implicit challenges. A learning module should allow a contemporary view of the diagnostic problem. The communication of this module should communicate an "open" assembly structure, providing students with a "layout" of activities, promoting a critical view and a playful perspective and implementing a process rather than a formula. The learning experience develops a "conceptual tool" perspective including different concepts and stages of development. The visual exploratory evaluation also allows to reflect on the image curation and how this practice will influence later "intuitive" choices of visual information.

- Fostering interest in the construction of project value through the promotion of elements of visual literacy and creation of visual narratives.

Through the structuring of exploratory models, students can develop different solutions for the different phases of the diagnosis, allowing different outputs of the project, in the phase of collecting visual elements, the symbolic elements, restricted to different cultures, gain a new relevance in argumentation and design logic.

Concerning the research specific objectives:

- Exploring the possibilities of co-creation arising from a visual exploratory phase.

The exploratory visual diagnostic study allows students to "think" with images, constituting these, objects of visual literacy.

- To contribute to an interventionist research methodology to build, with the use of Vnas (Visual Narrative Art Boards), an initial element of project development;

The Visual Diagnostic Models are pluralistic and have a sequential nature. They allow the incorporation of different information filters and are coherent in the objective of providing an evaluation base capable of "orienting" and "nurturing" the conduct of the project in a sequential and convergent way. Allowing students to structure an "informed" path within a reflexive strategy, where the student thinks about their project thinking, as it is possible to observe in the examples regarding the implementation of a (Visual Diagnostic Exploratory Study) (José Silva et al., 2020), POST-TEXTUAL ELEMENTS, *Figure 38-40*.

- Value integrative creative methodologies that converge in a learning group;

The VNA's allow creative itineraries, resulting from the composition of multiple visual cultural mosaics

- Contributing to a basis for critical reflection prior to digital interaction and manipulation.

The visual elements resulting from VNA's suggest narratives and these allow different visual associations and interpretations, driven and supported by the image reasoning, promote visual culture and help students, through a dialogue of co-creation in leveraging critical thinking.

The results of the last published article, Innovation in Traditional Productive Sectors - Visual Curation in Design (Jose Silva et al., 2020), point to the application of the principle of visual diagnosis in the construction of strategies supported in image curation as argumentative support both in experimental development as well as in product communication.

At the level of the effectiveness of the visual diagnostic exploratory study, it can guide creativity solutions delimited by three perspectives, archetypes, product cultural code, and customer journey. These three levels are operated as information filters and allow for greater security in the project's argumentation and safety in the development of the project, to some extent alleviating the "cognitive load" of the challenge presented by the project.

The difficulties experienced in positioning the archetypes to happen, and students show some problems understanding the potential consumer's perspective. In this sense, it is essential to include a standpoint of consumer behaviors and product potentiality in the student's perception. Using a metaphor, the designer should be a constant advocate of the product; from this, students can wield visual arguments from different contexts that "defend" the product.

The difficulties felt in creating customer narratives are associated with difficulty in externalizing an intuitive knowledge about consumer practices and vehicles. These channels are the social platforms that students use in everyday life, characterized by the dominant role of the image. The students know these consumption channels intimately, but because they do not consider them "prestigious," they do not externalize them.

The image is not merely graphic content without connection with real life because it is, after all, due to the behaviors it communicates, it can trigger a series of interactions with reality. The visual diagnostic exploratory study allows students to think with images more consciously by drawing attention to the need for culturally delimited visual literacy. In this way, it reinforces future designers' responsibility when developing communication solutions for products and services.

The next subchapter presents the dissemination related with the post doc research.

6.1 Research Dissemination

As a result of the epistemic process related to the project **Value Co-creation in Digital Design through Visual Exploratory Assessment**, the following articles were produced, summarizing the following results:

Articles	Results
<p>Silva, Jose, Neves, J., & Raposo, D. (2016). Image diagnostic as foundation for communication design development - learning module design. In 4.a CIDAG - Conferencia Internacional em Design e Artes Graficas. CIDAG.</p>	<p>A learning module on Visual Diagnostics in Design can contribute new insights to learning when it presents a strategy supported by explicit and implicit objectives. A learning module should reflect a contemporary view of the diagnostic component and allow students to test different concepts in visual discovery.</p>
<p>Silva, José, Raposo, D., & Neves, J. (2018). Product and brand, design insights from myth dissemination - Learning module. IV International Congress in Branding - New Developments to Individual and Collective Well-Being. Brand Trends, 14(14), 30–41.</p>	<p>The implicit strategy of a learning module in Communication Design communicated to students, along with their learning experience, allows them to understand critically, cultural "resources" of communication, in the perspective of a "creative tool". The test of solutions in social media, allows to prove the effectiveness of the results and the "creative tool".</p>
<p>Silva, José, Raposo, D., Neves, J., & Silva, F. (2018). Visual Storytelling As A Learning Creative Strategy: An Itinerary Through A Mosaic Of Visual Clues. In C. Moura & F. Paiva (Eds.), DESIGNA 2018 - Territory (1st ed., pp. 235–244). LABCOM.IFP, UBI.</p>	<p>Visual storytelling, via visual mosaics, is a creative itinerary of guidance, which nourishes exploration in the diagnostic phase. Where analogies and visual metaphors are used to define concepts. It allows for "synetic" perspectives, makes the familiar stranger and the familiar stranger.</p>
<p>Silva, José, Martins, D., & Neves, J. (2020). Visual Diagnostic Strategy: Design Learning Strategy. In Handbook of Research on Driving Industrial Competitiveness With Innovative Design Principles (p. 300). https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-3628-5</p>	<p>A visual, sequential diagnostic can contain, different "modules", each module works as an information filter. The use of three perspectives, archetypes, cultural code of the product and customer journey allows in a monochronic way to relieve the "cognitive load" of the challenge presented by the project, delaying anticipatory thoughts of the "results" of the project.</p>
<p>Silva, Jose, Raposo, D., Neves, J., & da Silva, F. M. (2020). Visual Storytelling - Creative Strategy of Visual Clues Promoted by Archetypal Images. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-20227-9_26</p>	<p>An archetypal correspondence map, built on the basis of Communication and Marketing literature, can be used as an information filter. The map is a support to understanding the importance of cultural indexing of images. The "Archetypal Institutions" structure narratives and contextualize visual exploration from a visual diagnostic perspective, as support in Communication design projects.</p>
<p>Silva, Jose, Raposo, D., Neves, J., Ribeiro, R., Marto, I., & Silva, F. (2020). Innovation in Traditional Productive Sectors - Visual Curation in Design. In J. Raposo, Daniel Neves, J. Silva, L. C. Castilho, & R. Dias (Eds.), Advances in Ergonomics in Design. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-51038-1_11</p>	<p>Visual product narratives are a bridge of reflection and dialogue between entrepreneurs (Small and Middle companies) and designers in communication and even in the discovery of new product solutions. The VCDM (Visual Communication Diagnostic Methodology) method, by including three information filters; archetypes, product cultural code and customer journey. enables solutions to guide creativity and communication in the project team.</p>

Table 3 - Summary table of articles produced within the scope of the Value Co-creation in Digital Design through Visual Exploratory Assessment investigation and its conclusions.

The results of the epistemic path lead to the concept of interface supporting the development of an information curation perspective:

- A learning module on the subject of Visual Diagnosis must contain an explicit and implicit strategy. Explicit conjugation of variables of analysis avoiding anticipatory conclusions at the beginning of the project. Implicit in visual literacy and information filtering and categorization.

- Visual results allow different visual narratives and location points to be curated. The location point on the visual map is a perspective and an interface with interlocutors representing the theme explored visually

6.2 Future Research Avenues

Resulting from the research Value Co-creation in Digital Design through Visual Exploratory Assessment, and specifically from the last article produced, arises the proposal of the following theme; the role of visual curation as a contribution to the development of interfaces between academia and business. This theme operates as an implicit question and problem of the contribution of the present research proposal: How to start a project? This problem is contextualized in the field of imaging diagnosis and measures the problem of building a visual literacy base. Visual literacy as a basis of reflection and positioning of a product or service framed in a social, cultural and economic context, starting from the premise of a positioning in space, by Aby Warburg (McEwan, 2006) and the creation of new reasonings by the organization and disposition of materials (Potter, 2012). In this sense, the question involves a clue for the deconstruction of a temporal and spatial positioning, favoring contexts, similarities and metaphors for a project dynamic.

The competencies and capabilities needed to live and learn in a society undergoing a digital transformation relate to fostering learning and highlighting the "moldable" and interconnectivity of technology to the "human" ecosystem.

Resilience in individuals, communities, and ecosystems probably depends on a required balance between eudemonic and reflexive thought.

Technology, when allowing strategies of (circuits design), where users combine different operations and tools becomes a tactic resource, where beyond the strategic use in larger timetable scenarios, has an essential role in daily scenarios that cope with cognitive load resultant from work or information efforts.

Individuals portray an important role in delivering human experiences, narratives, and perspectives. Technology delivers the tool and the creative mainframe through (circuits design)

Teachers can help as facilitators, recognizing the perspectives in transcodification allocating that effort to empower the co-creation with digital tools.

Educational institutions can test new paradigms, updating new strategies, and empowering the envision and test of multiple scenarios. They also have a huge importance in adapt and mainstream the pedagogical use of new and emerging technologies through a problem definition effort. Schools can adequately work the problem definition by a "wicked" problem approach, ill-defined Problems: both problem and solution are unknown initially. A large part of the problem solving is defining the problem. Only possible through an empathy connection with the final user.

The future Research will address the development of interfaces between businesses and the Academy where visual curation Practices can generate communication practice interfaces and different product perception perspectives. The Academy can provide scientific analysis and, due to its different audiences, can provide a laboratory of different meanings about a product. The healing requires a mapping that other strategies like Serious Lego Play can trigger, increasing strengths and optimizing the functionality of a project. Optimization is related to selecting and prioritizing information in competitive scenarios and commercial partnerships.

A strong link can result from a basic disciplinary approach “Mode 1” teaching and research on the one hand and multidisciplinary approach “Mode 2” applied and strategic research and training on the other.

There are different forms of knowledge production, beginning particularly with the work of Gibbons et al(1994) and Scott (1995). The traditional view of academic knowledge based on discrete disciplines, and ‘pure’ research arising out of those disciplines, relate to ‘Mode 1’. Its cognitive and social norms determine what the significant problems are, who is allowed to practice science, and what constitutes good science. A more recent view regards knowledge production as ‘intrinsically trans-disciplinary, trans-institutional and heterogeneous’ (Cele, 2005, p. 2). This second type of knowledge production – which has become known as ‘Mode 2’ – is problem-oriented, deals with knowledge developed in the context of application and (often) partnerships, and accommodates aspects of social responsibility. The element of work across disciplines is key to this mode.

Asplund & Bengtsson(2004) developed a model for structuring an arena for supporting more elaborated learning and teaching, including three arenas: the student, the company, and the teaching. As a basic framework, Dunkin and Biddle (1975) introduced a pedagogical model called the 3P-model of learning and teaching, which can introduce the process of learning and teaching divided into three distinct factors: presage, process and product.

The first factor is the Presage factor which includes three kinds of contexts: a) student, b) company/managers, and c) teaching contexts.

The student context focuses on the student and the relevant prior knowledge the student has about the topic, their interest in the topic, and the student's abilities. The organization/ company context includes the managers' or managers' prior knowledge on the topic, prior education, prior experience of interaction with students and the university, the company's current (for example, technology strategy) situation, and the culture of the whole company.

Finally, is the teaching context. It includes the actual course topic, the pedagogical format, the teacher's/faculties expertise, factual knowledge, teaching skills and the culture of the whole class group. The Process is the second factor and highlights the learning-focused activities and processes that are applied and used by all three actors, i.e., the students, company, and teachers/faculty different learning strategies.

The third factor is the Product which shows the learning outcome for the three stakeholders. The outcomes result from the following areas: a) What learners learned about the topic, b) How they learned it, and c) How the student/ company/faculty got involved in the learning process. The teacher's context relates to what the teachers do (i.e., intervene) to create good conditions for individual and collective learning. The learning outcome (the "product") is, therefore, what we learn (as students, teachers, and managers), how we learn it, and the personal relationships we have to this new knowledge, systems, and the learning process

Edquist (1997), Meeus et al. (2001) and (2002) point out that knowledge institutions can be recognized as interfacing units that link innovating firms to external actors and facilitate information and technology transfer as well as technological collaboration.

In an experimental axis, the Academy can create more tangible interfaces that operate a gain of perspective intersecting more traditional visions with different perspectives of consumption and development.

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8 POST-TEXTUAL ELEMENTS

8.1 Project briefing - Visual Diagnostic Exploratory Study

The briefing presented in the curricular year of 2018/19 was structured in 3 phases **Figure 37 – 48**, through 8 guided sessions in which the teacher had a role as a study companion. An informed travel companion accompanies students in the expanded field of design (Hardman, 2018).

Figure 37 - Design Briefing (Visual Diagnostic Exploratory Study), course Research Design.

Figure 38 - Student Joana Dias final example panel.

Due to the copyright of the images used, the images were purposely pixelated. The image column on the right shows the summary of the whole process (José Silva, Martins, & Neves, 2020).

Concept Represented in two or three words
+
Their image representation

Figure 39 - Student Beatriz Vidal final example panel.

Figure 40 - Ana Catarina Martins final example panel.

DIAGNÓSTICO

VALORES DE ARQUÉTIPOS EMOCIONAIS

SÃO TOMÉ E PRÍNCIPE

Saved Time: 1 min

Summary Keywords Key fragments

Foi quando nasci em 1995 que passei pela minha primeira experiência com a medicina tradicional, é algo que está inserido na cultura africana e nomeadamente a santomense.

No meu caso, o meu contacto com essa prática deve-se ao facto de ter nascido em casa e a minha mãe não tinha forças suficientes para chegar a tempo ao hospital, então chamou-se a parteira tradicional que no momento era a escolha mais acertada a fazer.

Na altura, devido as instabilidades a nível de saúde convencional as pessoas optavam pelo método tradicional.

tradicional que dizia "é essencial reconhecemos e aprendemos mais com a Medicina Tradicional Africana."

Saved Time: 1 min

Summary Keywords Key fragments

Informação Keywords

No meu caso, o meu contacto com essa prática deve-se ao facto de ter nascido em casa e a minha mãe não tinha forças suficientes para chegar a tempo ao hospital, então chamou-se a parteira tradicional que no momento era a escolha mais acertada a fazer.

Saved Time: 1 min

Summary Keywords Key fragments

A minha pesquisa foi feita em torno do tema "Remédios Tradicionais" em São Tomé e Príncipe, tema este que apresenta muitos conceitos inerentes à cultura africana e nomeadamente santomense. No diagnóstico para a descoberta de valores de arquétipos emocionais ligados a prática da medicina tradicional, com base no sistema de José Martins, extrai arquétipos como: Idealismo, cenas do dia-a-dia, sensibilidade e poder da união da humanidade. Com base na descodificação destes arquétipos, conclui-se que o código cultural de São Tomé e Príncipe é o código "LEVE LEVE". O "LEVE LEVE" é a expressão usada em São Tomé para dizer que tudo é feito pouco, sem pressa e sem stress. Este código foi extraído através de imagens ligadas a cada arquétipo emocional acima mencionado que mais definem a cultura santomense. Após o diagnóstico para se perceber os valores emocionais ligados a prática da medicina tradicional, seguiu-se para a análise de código cultural extraído, realizando uma análise de experiências de testemunhos, utilizando o método de Clotilde Rapaille. Este método serve de análise de padrões descobertos com base num texto que relata histórias de experiências vividas pelas pessoas que passaram pela mesma situação, estruturando assim a informação. A jornada do consumidor foi desenvolvida em resposta ao método de Clotilde Rapaille, e serve de estratégia que visa a tornar explícita a informação implícita através da utilização de uma narrativa que está relacionada com o comportamento do consumidor. Para finalizar o diagnóstico, seleccionei três imagens que definem o tema, que posteriormente deu origem ao conceito por detrás da prática da medicina tradicional. A escolha do filme "Curandeiro do Jaré" deve-se ao facto de ter uma ligação super directa com o tema abordado, é um filme que relata o dia-a-dia do curandeiro e os valores culturais por detrás desta prática. O final deste diagnóstico é a fusão destes mesmos diagnósticos que é a cara através de métodos tradicionais. Na segunda fase podemos sumarizar os elementos textuais em imagens que de forma mais intuitiva caracterizam os elementos investigados.

Jornada do Consumidor

(Consumer Journey)

COMPORTAMENTO DO CONSUMIDOR

Figure 41 - Elisangila Cruz final example panel.

A primeira vez que me lembro ter contacto com mirtilos foi mesmo numa fase mais adulta, em que consumi os mesmos rum logarte.

Decidi arrancar e acabei por comprar uma caixa de mirtilos.

Aquele sabor é deslumbrante, depois mais tarde consegui comprar aos baldes e fazer doce, sempre que posso faço e a minha família adora!.

Bem, na minha primeira experiência com mirtilos estava um pouco reticente, no entanto provei e até gostei.

Deve ter sido na primavera/verão e a sensação foi que tinham uma textura um bocadinho estranha.

Bem, a minha primeira experiência com mirtilos foi na minha festa de aniversário, quando fiz uns 12 anos, e o bolo trazia frutos vermelhos.

A minha primeira prova e experiência com o mirtilo ocorreu quando a minha mãe decidiu fazer uma tarte de mirtilo.

Para ser sincera, na primeira impressão não gostei muito da textura que a minha mãe fez para o recheio da tarte.

Quando penso no conceito mirtilo, recordo-me da minha mãe comprar logartes com aroma à fruta do bosque.

Esses logartes tornaram-se os meus preferidos, devido ao seu sabor intenso.

Informative Kognativa

- vinho para
- vinho
- leite
- fermento
- fermento prova
- mirtilo
- fermentado
- aroma
- leite
- destaque

[com mirtilos foi mesmo numa fase adulta, em que consumi os mesmos rum logarte](#)

[mirtilos foi em casa](#)

[sabor é deslumbrante](#)

[família adora!](#)

[primeira tinha plantação](#)

[com mirtilos estava pouco](#)

[bolo trazia frutos](#)

[com mirtilos foi na](#)

[mirtilos eram como limões](#)

[Na altura fizeti com ideia](#)

[mãe decidiu fazer tarte](#)

[mãe fez para recheio](#)

[mãe comprar logartes](#)

[de destaque seria mirtilo](#)

[logartes tornaram-se preferidos](#)

Experimentei mirtilo pela primeira vez por curiosidade.

Tinha 6 anos quando provei mirtilos pela primeira vez.

1 A Maria e o marido foram almoçar a um restaurante.

2 Enquanto almoçavam ela apercebe-se de que o marido está a olhar fixamente para uma rapariga mais nova. Esta apresenta uma aparência juvenil e saudável.

3 Este contrasto gera uma pequena discussão entre o casal.

4 Mais tarde já em casa, a Maria não consegue deixar de se ver ao espelho e sentir-se mal com a sua aparência.

5 Pega no telemóvel e pesquisa dicas para pele mais jovem e saudável e acaba por encontrar uma publicação sobre os benefícios do mirtilo para a saúde e estética.

6 Decide então ir ao supermercado comprar mirtilos devido às suas propriedades antioxidantes.

7 Desde aí começou, junto com a família, a introduzir este fruto na sua alimentação e a praticar um estilo de vida mais saudável.

8 Maria sente-se rejuvenescida e, de novo, bem consigo mesma.

Figure 42 - Liliana Almeida final example panel.

Figure 43 - Marta Sofia final example panel.

Figure 44 - Maria Rodrigues final example panel.

Emotional Archetypes Reference Chart

Emotion	Archetype	Image
Power	Power of Humanity	[Image]
Global	Global Tribe	[Image]
Scenes	Scenes of Everyday	[Image]
Socialization	Socialization	[Image]
Idealism	Idealism	[Image]

1 Emotional archetypes selected

- Socialization
- Scenes of Everyday
- Power of Humanity
- Idealism

2 Vector strength distribution in star configuration

3 Ordering Emotional Archetypes by levels of importance

- 1 Power of Humanity
- 2 Global Tribe
- 3 Scenes of Everyday
- 4 Socialization
- 5 Idealism

4 Discovering Cultural Images Stereotypes related to the Emotional Archetypes images (7 Strategy to sort Martins (2007) archetypes and their images by archetype)

Empowering Visual Literacy on a product design related to the Emotional Archetypes images (7 Strategy to sort Martins (2007) archetypes and their images by archetype)

Power of Humanity Global Tribe Scenes of Everyday Socialization Idealism

Summary **Keywords** **Key Fragments**

No debate público, o fenómeno migratório é maioritariamente tratado como "um problema e uma ameaça para as sociedades" e, por isso, imigrantes e refugiados "precisam ser controlados, regulados ou mesmo contidos", aponta Denise Crisp à IREJ On-Line na entrevista concedida por e-mail.

Apesar desta narrativa, a jornalista Rita a importância de "desconstruirmos alguns desses discursos produzidos e reproduzidos historicamente em relação ao 'não nacional' ou ao 'outro' e compreendermos as migrações como uma experiência humana que historicamente traz contribuições sociais, culturais, políticas e económicas às sociedades, assim como pensar a mobilidade como um direito humano e universal".

Para que uma narrativa positiva sobre o fenómeno migratório seja possível, explica, "precisamos desnaturalizar a ideia de fronteiras geográficas e de nacionalidade e entendê-las como uma construção histórica que decorre de disputas geopolíticas, socioculturais e económicas".

Dados de 2017 da Anuar (agência da ONU para Refugiados) indicam que 83% das pessoas refugiadas vivem em países empobrecidos que recebem uma ajuda excessiva para seu atendimento.

Informative Keywords

- Debate público
- Anti-migração
- Mundo migratório
- Debate público
- Paz

[pessoas refugiadas vivem em países empobrecidos](#)

[ciudadanos refugiados vivem em países empobrecidos](#)

[dados divulgados pela ONU: São The Children](#)

[Denise Crisp é trabalhadora em formalização](#)

[políticas anti-imigrantes afetadas, migrantes, trauma](#)

[pessoas refugiadas vivem em países empobrecidos](#)

[acordos de cooperação económica Brasil](#)

[sistema de refugiados: divulgado pela Christian na Internacional](#)

Migração
 Mundo
 Município
 Anti-Migração
 Debate Público
 Paz

+

Variedade - **COR**
 Globo - **PLANETA**
 Símbolos - **CRAYO**

1. Rania tem 5 anos e vive com o irmão Ibrahim, na Líbia com os seus pais. 2. Infelizmente, a família é obrigada a sair do seu país. O país está em Guerra. 3. Em desespero, Rania foge mais a mãe, para a Europa, enquanto o pai fica em território com o Ibrahim. 4. A viagem é de risco e atribulada 5. Ao chegar à Europa, o sonho transforma-se num novo sofrimento.

6. Felizmente, conseguem ter ajuda humanitária e o visto de refugiadas. 7. Graças aos protocolos europeus, são convidadas a ter uma segunda oportunidade de vida, em Castelo Branco, Portugal. 8. Mais tarde, depois de estabelecer relações emocionais e sociais na cidade de acolhimento, conseguem fazer com que o resto da família, venha ter com elas.

Saúde e Bem-Estar **Educação e Qualidade** **Igualdade de Género** **Trabalho Decente e Crescimento Económico** **Resiliência das Desigualdades** **Paz, Justiça e Inclusão dos Migrantes**

Avaliação crítica

Críticas e necessidades

Críticas e necessidades

+

Figure 45 - João Batista final example panel.

Figure 46 - Joana Candeias final example panel.

Figure 47 - Catarina Martins final example panel.

Emotional Archetypes Reference Chart

Image Type	Archetype	Root	Safety	Personal	Power of union of Humanity	Sensibility	Energy flow
Self							
Self Esteem							
Power of union of Humanity							
Sensibility							
Energy flow							
Root							

1 Emotional archetypes selected

- Root
- Safety
- Personal
- Power of union of Humanity
- Sensibility
- Energy flow
- Self Esteem
- Idealism

2 Vector strength distribution in star configuration

3 Ordering Emotional Archetypes by levels of importance

- 1 Safety, Self Esteem
- 2 Sensibility, Personal
- 3 Power of union of Humanity
- 4 Energy flow, Idealism
- 4 Root

4 Discovering Cultural Images Stereotypes related to the Emotional Archetypes

Empowering Visual Literacy on a product design Strategy to sort Martins (2007) archetypes and their image definition according to image stereotypes.

Summary | **Keywords** | **Key Fragments**

Eu fui a Fátima porque a minha avó acredita na nossa senhora de Fátima e teve que ir a Fátima para arranjar uma solução.
 O que me leva ate Fátima é a fé e a sensação de paz que todo o espaço transmite.
 Vou a Fátima assistir à missa, mas só vou lá na concentração de rezar.

Informative Keywords

[avó acredita na](#)
 Eu fui a Fátima porque a minha avó acredita na nossa senhora de Fátima e teve que ir a Fátima para arranjar uma solução.

[vou a Fátima a fé](#)
 O que me leva ate Fátima é a fé e a sensação de paz que todo o espaço transmite.

[Fátima assistir missa](#)
 Vou a Fátima assistir à missa, mas só vou lá na concentração de rezar.

[família vai à missa](#)
 Normalmente a minha família vai à missa e depois acabamos por alhoofar por lá.

[Fátima pagar promessa](#)
 Vou a Fátima pagar uma promessa, a minha filha está muito mal e preciso de ajuda.

Contextualizing the Consumer Journey narrative visual context

1 - Francisco, bailarino há pouco tempo, mas adora aquilo que faz.
2 - O Francisco vai ter uma tournée de ballet daqui a um mês e anda a esforçar-se imenso nos treinos.
3 - A um mês da competição o Francisco lesiona-se.
4 - Infelizmente o Francisco tem que pausar os treinos, mas como ele é tão apaixonado por aquilo que faz ele não desiste... Um pouco abalado com toda a situação ele decide ir a Fátima. Recorre à fé para aliviar a dor e para superar este obstáculo.
5 - Ao chegar lá, o Francisco partilha nas redes sociais o sítio, a comida, a música por se levar e comprar umas recordações para a família.
6 - A duas semanas da competição, o Francisco sente-se muito melhor e consegue o seu primeiro troféu!

Self Esteem
Power of union of humanity
Sensibility
Energy flow

+

Story gist

Figure 48 - Ana Lopes final example panel.

